

**Analysis and Assessment of Pre- and Post-Test Survey Results
for Climate Change and Green Skills Modules in an Educational App**

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Author's Notes

The surveys on which this study is based were conducted by Plan International Pilipinas from August to September 2024 in two phases with the aim to evaluate the effectiveness of their intervention using the *Hope Town Hero* app. I was commissioned by the organization in November to analyze and assess the results of the surveys and accordingly make some recommendations to further develop the app.

I have no personal stake to disclose in this project. All findings, recommendations, and conclusions, are all data driven, processed and analyzed using relevant statistical tools.

Abstract

This research investigates the potentials of the *Hope Town Hero* (HTH) app as an innovative tool to promote green skills and climate change education among children and youth. Grounded in the urgent need for widespread climate literacy, this study examines the effectiveness of integrating education into educational strategies, with a particular focus on the Philippines. The research method employs pre- and post-test surveys, qualitative feedback, and demographic data to assess the app's effectiveness. Quantitative analysis reveals trends in knowledge acquisition and behavioral intentions, while qualitative insights from user feedback inform recommendations for enhancing the app. Findings show significant improvements in users' understanding of green skills and climate issues. Recommendations include refining the user experience, expanding content coverage, and conducting longitudinal studies to evaluate long-term impacts. The research concludes that educational apps like HTH hold substantial promise in equipping the next generation with the knowledge and skills needed to address climate challenges effectively.

Keywords: Climate change education, green skills, gamification

Table of Contents

Abstract	2
Overview on Climate Change	8
Climate Change Education	8
The Role of Children and Youth	9
The Gap in Climate Change Education in the Philippines	13
Objectives of the Study	14
General Objectives	15
Specific Objectives	15
Review of Related Literature	16
Play-learning as a Method of Teaching	16
Definition of Gamification, Pitfalls, and How to Avoid Them	16
Challenging Scenarios	17
Reward and Punishment	17
Pitfalls of Gamification and How to Avoid Them	17
Duolingo®: A Case Study	19
Focus on the Essentials	20
What is Fun is Memorable	20
Personalization	20
User-friendly Interface	21
Learning Using Various Methods	21
Key Performance Indicators	21
Product Stickiness	21
Product Adoption	22
Product Growth	22
Product Engagement Score	22
Climate Change Education Goals and Paradigm	22
KPIs for Climate Change Education	24
Climate Change Education Implementation	24
Professional Development	25
Curriculum Development	25
Climate Change as a Body of Knowledge	26
Methodology	26
Data Collection	26
Respondent Selection	27
Survey Structure and Strategy	27
Question Categories and Their Purpose	28
Recommendations	31

Results and Discussion	31
Demographics	32
Gender, LGBTQ+ Distribution Across Provinces	34
Indigenous People Distribution Across Provinces	37
Pre-Test and Post Test Results	38
What the Diagnostics Tell Us	38
Effects of Climate Change on Key Areas of Society	49
Levels of Interest, Knowledge, and Frequency	52
Awareness and Understanding of Green Jobs	59
Confidence to Face the Future	66
Environmentally Positive Actions	69
What Young People Can Already Do	71
Post-Test Questions	75
Green Jobs	80
Conclusion	82
Recommendations	83
Revisit and Redesign the Curriculum	86
K-12 Curriculum Mapping	86
Hope Town Hero Image	94
Marketing Collaterals	95
A Note on Adultification	96
Core Features and Game Structure	97
Periodic Evaluation	102

LIST OF TABLES

1	Sample set of probing questions in the survey instrument	28
2	Pre- and post-test gender distribution of respondents	31
3	Pre- and post-test provincial distribution of respondents	33
4	Pre-test provincial distribution of gender, LGBTQ+, IPs, and trained	36
5	Pre-test and post-test results of untrained male (UM) and untrained female (UF), trained male (TM) and trained female (TF)	39

6	Pre-test results of untrained male and female (UM,UF); trained male and female (TM, TF); average of UM, UF (AUMF); average of TM and TF (ATMF); Post-test results of male and female who trained using <i>Hope Town Hero</i> (HTH-M, HTH-F); average of HTH-M and HTH-F (AHTH-MF)	43
7	Comparison between post-test and pre-test male (trained) and post-test and pre-test female (trained)	45
8	Post-test and pre-test results from respondents from the LGBTQ+ community	48
9	Perceived effect of Cc on key areas	49
10	Levels of interest and knowledge of respondents on various environmental topics, and frequency of them observing positive measures for the environment	52
11	Pre- and post-test results on the green jobs awareness or knowledge of the respondents	59
12	Perceived challenges in the future	63
13	Factors that will help the respondents to be confident	66
14	Environmentally positive actions the respondents do	70
15	Top 8 responses of the participants across all areas	72
16	Top 2 responses of the participants across all areas	75
17	Top 20 things learned by the respondents	73
18	Examples of green jobs, and what prevents people from finding a green job.	79
19	Sample skills / competencies that may be developed in a user of <i>Hope Town Hero</i>	91
20	Recommended KPI for HTH	101

LIST OF FIGURES

1	Impact of training on both M and F participants	40
2	TM vs TF	41
3	UM vs UF	41
4	UMF vs HTH-MF	42
5	Performance of untrained MF and HTH-MF	46
6	Levels of knowledge of the respondents in various environmental topics	53
7	Comparison between pre-test and post-test on perceived impact of Cc on key areas	50
8	Levels of interest of the respondents in various environmental topics	53
9	Levels of knowledge of the respondents in various environmental topics	55
10	Levels of frequency of the respondents in various environmental topics	57
11	Radar chart comparing pre- and post-test date on perceived challenges	64
12	Environmentally positive actions the respondents do	71

ABBREVIATIONS USED

The author uses the following abbreviations for long words or phrases frequently repeated in this paper. These abbreviations are particularly useful for presentation purposes, such as in tables and graphs, but they are not standard anywhere or officially accepted abbreviations.

CC	Climate change
E.SMR	Eastern Samar
HTH	<i>Hope Town Hero</i>
HTH-M/F	A male and/or female participant who had used the HTH app
MAG	Maguindanao
N.SMR	Northern Samar
NB	Non-binary, or somebody has not yet decided to which gender they belong.
PIP	Plan International Pilipinas
RES	Responses in a survey
TF	Trained Female, a respondent who has undergone a special class on a horse.
TM	Trained Male (same explanation as above)
TMF	Trained Male and Female
UF	Untrained Female (same explanation as UM)
UM	Untrained Male, a respondent who has not yet undergone a PIP training on CC
UMF	Untrained Male and/or Female
UNCRTN	Uncertain
W.SMR	Western Samar

Overview on Climate Change

Climate change, driven by both natural and human activities, leads to significant environmental degradation.¹ If current trends continue, Earth will lose many of its natural resources and will no longer be able to support life as we know it. Activities such as deforestation and pollution of air and water contribute to the gradual increase in Earth's surface temperature. This slow but steady rise in temperature has already begun to show its effects. Natural calamities like hurricanes, heatwaves, floods, and droughts are becoming more intense, widespread, and frequent. The 21st century has become a century of calamities.² These natural disasters are Earth's way of calling for our attention and help. Unless we respond, the loss of human lives and property will continue to escalate.

Climate Change Education

Humans are both the culprits and the victims of climate change, yet they also hold the key to their own salvation. The journey from ignorance to enthusiastic advocacy for the responsible and sustainable use of natural resources lies in the power of education.

Climate change defines the present reality and will shape humanity's future. The fight to save the planet from further decline depends on everyone's willingness to act and change.

¹ "Environmental Degradation Causes, Effects and Solutions." 15 Mar. 2023, <https://plantwithpurpose.org/causes-effects-and-solutions-to-environmental-degradation/>

² "Understanding and governing global systemic crises in the 21st century" 14 Mar. 2023, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/1758-5899.13192>.

While world leaders negotiate accords, treaties, and policies to combat climate change, the success of these efforts hinges on the actions and behaviors of individuals.

History has shown that revolutions sparking positive change occur when ordinary people unite toward a common goal, each making a contribution to that shared purpose.

If individual knowledge, attitudes, and habits can be transformed to prioritize environmental stewardship, the health of the planet will significantly improve. Education, particularly among the youth, serves as the foundation for this transformation, empowering future generations to take responsible action and drive sustainable change.

The Role of Children and Youth

An inquiry into the state of knowledge of young people regarding Climate change and their attitudes toward the environment is vital, as they will bear the greatest burden of global warming's impacts. Their cooperation and active involvement are essential in this collective battle for the survival of humanity.

According to data from the Department of Education (DepEd) on their Enhanced Basic Education Information System (EBEIS), from school year 2009-2010 to 2017-2018, 43,810 out of 47,000 public schools in the Philippines experienced natural calamities. Over these eight years, tropical cyclones damaged 39,738 schools, floods affected 25,191 schools, and 5,824 schools were in

vulnerable coastal areas.³ These natural hazards not only interrupt the delivery of education, but children in affected areas become vulnerable to diseases, and they can also experience hunger due to loss of the job of a breadwinner or the livelihood of their family.

Educating the youth about environmental challenges, their causes and effects, and mitigation strategies is crucial. Equipping them with practical green skills, such as gardening, energy conservation, and tree planting, among others; and encouraging their habitual application ensures that they are prepared to address environmental challenges and contribute to a sustainable future.

Non-government organizations (NGOs) advocating for environmental protection have increasingly engaged children in advancing this cause. For example, the term “Green Ambassadors”⁴ is used by NGOs to inspire children and youth to promote the sustainable use of natural resources.⁵ The strategy focuses on educating young people and training them to teach others. In this role, children help spread awareness to their peers, schools, and communities about environmental degradation and ways to prevent it.

This approach is rooted in the proven teaching method of peer teaching, where children assume both the roles of teacher and learner in a spirit of

³ Department of Education (n.d.). *The Need for Climate Change Education*. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/climate-change-education/cce-in-the-philippines/>

⁴ "Green Ambassadors - Maryland Association for Environmental and Outdoor" <https://www.maeoe.org/what-we-do/maryland-green-schools-program/green-ambassadors/>.

⁵ "Green Ambassadors Club." 10 Jan. 2022, <https://greenambassadorsclub.org/>.

collaboration.⁶ Research shows that children can be highly effective peer educators,⁷ and this strategy accelerates the dissemination of knowledge on climate change while making learning more engaging and enjoyable.

Moreover, children possess the advantage of time. A seven-year-old who learns during their formative years the importance of environmental stewardship can create a lifelong impact, benefiting the planet and its inhabitants over decades.

On the grand stage of environmental activism, the voices of children, though gentle, can resonate powerfully. An American Indian proverb aptly states, "We do not inherit the Earth from our ancestors; we borrow it from our children."⁸ This timeless wisdom emphasizes the critical role of children and youth in addressing environmental issues. The Earth belongs to them, and today's adults bear a responsibility to be accountable to these future stewards of the planet.

Recognizing this principle, children deserve a platform of respect to share their views and concerns. Adults must not only listen but also respond to their calls for action and, where appropriate, follow their advice.

A case study on International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), and their collaboration with young people in projects for the protection of the environment, underscores the positive impact of children and youth that led to the

⁶ Schunk, D. H. (1987). Peer Models and Children's Behavioral Change. *Review of Educational Research*, 57(2), 149-174. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543057002149>

⁷ "Peer Teaching: Overview, Benefits & Models | Together Mentoring Software." 11 Mar. 2024, <https://www.togetherplatform.com/blog/peer-teaching-overview-benefits-models>.

⁸ "We Do Not Inherit the Earth from Our Ancestors; We Borrow It from Our" 22 Jan. 2013, <https://quoteinvestigator.com/2013/01/22/borrow-earth/>.

success of their efforts for sustainable use of natural resources.⁹ They were able to mobilize youth from various backgrounds in conservation activities, which not only directly benefited the environment but raised the awareness of surrounding communities.

Studies such as these hint at the pivotal role in nurturing this process by instilling in young minds a profound sense of ownership of their planet and their future. Because with proper instruction, children can be equipped with the right knowledge and skills that can give them the power to drive meaningful change.

Children and youth can shape a world far better than what they have inherited. With over 2.2 billion children worldwide—two billion of whom live in developing countries¹⁰—their collective influence is undeniable. In the Philippines alone, children under the age of 15 account for 30.7%¹¹ of the population.

If even half or a quarter of these children could be trained to develop a love for the environment and demonstrate this love through simple acts—such as disposing of waste properly, recycling, conserving electricity, limiting the use of electronic devices, and encouraging others to do the same—the impact on efforts to mitigate climate change would be significant.

⁹ International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN). "Engaging Youth on Climate Change & Environmental Sustainability." IUCN, Commission on Education and Communication (CEC). Accessed December 20, 2024. <https://knowledge.unicef.org/resource/engaging-youth-climate-change-environmental-sustainability>

¹⁰ [How many children are there in the world? - UNICEF DATA](#)

¹¹ "Philippines: children population share 2023 - Statista." 05 Feb. 2024, <https://www.statista.com/statistics/678279/philippines-children-as-a-percentage-of-the-population/>.

The empowerment of children as advocates for sustainability holds immense promise. Their actions today can pave the way for a cleaner, healthier, and more resilient future for generations to come.

The Gap in Climate Change Education in the Philippines

The Department of Education, as one of the most heavily funded government agencies, is mandated to prepare Filipino children and youth for the challenges of the 21st century, a century of calamities especially for the Philippines.

DepEd upholds four Core Values that every Filipino learner should embody to become well-rounded individuals: 1) *Maka-Diyos* or God-fearing, 2) *Makatao* or pro-people, 3) *Makakalikasan* or pro-environment), and 4) *Makabansa* or pro-country. The third tenet, *Makakalikasan*, is particularly critical given the Philippines' vulnerability to climate change and being one of the most polluted countries in the world.

This challenge, which stems from the government's insufficient enforcement of environmental laws and the general public's indifference toward environmental issues,¹² undoubtedly highlights a significant gap between DepEd's aspirations and the actual behavior of learners when it comes to preserving the country's natural resources.

¹² "Environmental Attitudes and Behaviors in the Philippines - ResearchGate." 01 Oct. 2014, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/278785159_Environmental_Attitudes_and_Behaviors_in_the_Philippines.

A study titled “Attitude and behavior of senior high school students toward environmental conservation”¹³ seeks to know how much Filipino youth understand the importance of the environment to them, and how engaged they are with conservation efforts to address Climate change.

The study shows that while the students are generally aware of environmental issues, a gap still exists between their knowledge and their actual and habitual acts to save the environment. This is shown in the overall evaluation of their attitudes toward ecological behavior, including nature utilization, and government policies.

Their responses indicated indecisiveness, reflecting uncertain or intermediate attitudes, which can be due to insufficient skills to contribute to the solution of environmental problems in their communities.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to analyze and assess the pre- and post-test surveys conducted by Plan International Pilipinas to give recommendations on the design of *Hope Town Hero* app for Climate change education. However, since HTH is an educational app, such recommendations must take into consideration curriculum design and educational theories in relation to a learner’s growth areas, namely, cognitive, affective, and psychosocial.

¹³ Berame, J., et. al. (2022). Attitude and behavior of senior high school students toward environmental conservation. *Biodiversitas Journal of Biological Diversity*, 23.

The surveys tell us where the gap in Climate change education of Filipino children and youth lies; but for recommendations on making the app more effective to help bridge this gap, the HTH development team must turn to educational principles for guidance to produce an engaging and impactful educational tool for the environment.

Therefore, this study presents two objective categories. The General objective concerns the recommendations to be made for the development of the app, which depend on the second, Specific objectives, which concern curricular content, including teaching strategies incorporating gamification elements; and standard measures to assess learning and behavior. The Specific objectives cover three developmental areas, namely, Cognitive, Affective, and Psychosocial objectives.

General Objectives

This study aims to provide recommendations to Plan International Pilipinas for the design and development of an educational app focused on Climate change education and the development of green skills among children and youth.

Specific Objectives

The General objective requires a comprehensive examination of the design of an educational app for Climate change awareness and green skills development to ensure it effectively achieves its purpose.

PIP seeks to gamify the learning experience to deepen learners' understanding of Climate change and drive behavioral change that inspires positive environmental actions.

The specific objectives are provided as a part of the recommendations.

Review of Related Literature

The following literatures were selected because they 1) provide a basis for the algorithmic design of the HTH app, 2) serve as standard / benchmark for gamifying Climate change education, 3) lay the foundation for curriculum development and help determine curricular content, or 4) help in determining what success means for this endeavor.

Play-learning as a Method of Teaching

Learning Through Play is an infographic published by the UNICEF-Lego Foundation, advocating for the integration of play into learning activities at both home and school.¹⁴ The document highlights play-based learning as a central element in early childhood development, emphasizing its importance in preparing children for the challenges of the future. The Lego Foundation aligns its advocacy with UN Sustainable Development Goal IV, which focuses on ensuring quality education for all.

However, the foundation stresses that play-based learning should complement, not replace traditional education. It encourages educators to find

¹⁴ "Learning through play - UNICEF."
<https://www.unicef.org/sites/default/files/2018-12/UNICEF-Lego-Foundation-Learning-through-Play.pdf>.

creative ways for children to play and learn simultaneously, leveraging the inherent appeal of play to foster engagement.

The infographic further underscores that when joyful and engaging games are integrated into meaningful learning experiences, they not only accelerate learning but also help children retain knowledge for longer periods.

Definition of Gamification, Pitfalls, and How to Avoid Them

Interaction Design Foundation, on their website, defines “gamification” as using the elements and principles that make a game, and apply it to learning activities, such as those done inside a classroom to make it more fun for students.¹⁵ Gamification designer Celia Hodent explains how this integration can be possible.

Challenging Scenarios

As an example, she used the game *Fortnite* where the learners are put in a cave to fight zombies. But the weapon they use breaks, and so they must be skillful in using the materials they have around and improvise a weapon.

Hodent explains that this tactic puts the learner in a situation where creativity and flexibility becomes crucial for survival. Why this is important is because, outside the context of the game, or if they are in the real world, they would not likely have this experience that demanded so much from them.

Reward and Punishment

Another game, for example, is *ZRX: Zombies Run*. Designed to encourage users to run as a form of exercise. Hodent notes that the game makes running fun,

¹⁵ Interaction Design Foundation - IxDF. (2016, June 29). What is Gamification (GF)?. Interaction Design Foundation - IxDF. <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/topics/gamification>

and some people would not run if it were not fun. Also, there is a kind of reward and punishment system built into the game, which can encourage them even more.

Pitfalls of Gamification and How to Avoid Them

In connection, the foundation enumerated three pitfalls of gamification. They say that if done wrong, the very activity designed to deliver learning could be its hindrance. These three are manipulation, building a game, and magic painting.

Manipulation. Games are supposed to be enjoyable and should be beneficial to the user, so when it is designed to benefit the developers instead, it defeats the purpose of education.

Building a Game. Games are only for reinforcement or to supplement learning experience. The game itself should not be the focus, but the learning.

Magic Painting. The learning experience should be worthwhile and we do not pretend that it is good when it is not.

To avoid these pitfalls, the IDF suggests six things that designers and programmers need to take into consideration to successfully gamify a learning experience.

Understand User Needs and Preferences. To gamify an experience effectively, an understanding the needs of the users and what motivates them is important. Designs must be based on personas to tailor gamification elements to different user types.

Align Gamification Mechanics with User Goals. Gamification mechanics should align with users' goals and the system's purpose, motivating desired

behaviors in a natural way. Mechanics like points, badges, and challenges should enhance the user experience and engage them more effectively.

Tailor the System for All Stakeholders. Once the right gamification mechanics are chosen, it's crucial to adapt the system to meet stakeholder needs. This may involve balancing competitive and collaborative features based on the user base's diversity. The goal is to create an inclusive and engaging experience for all users.

Evaluate and Iterate. A key element of successful gamification is continuous evaluation, which includes usability testing and user feedback to assess engagement. Based on this input, adjustments may be needed to refine and sustain the experience, ensuring it remains effective and enjoyable over time.

Integrate Gamification Seamlessly. Gamification should be seamlessly integrated into the existing system to enhance the user experience without overwhelming it. Game elements should feel natural and add value to the user journey, rather than being an extra layer that distracts from the core purpose of the design.

Inspire Through Interactivity and Social Elements. To boost user engagement, designers should integrate interactivity and social elements, such as features that spark curiosity, encourage social sharing, or build community. These elements tap into the natural human desire for interaction and connection, significantly enhancing the overall experience.

Duolingo®: A Case Study

Duolingo is popular among users from diverse backgrounds and various ages. Incorporating the elements of a digital game, this app can effectively motivate users to learn a new language. The app has the following general features to motivate and ensure continued engagement, such as streaks for daily attendance, leaderboards for competition, and rewards like virtual currency.¹⁶

Focus on the Essentials

Language study can be an ongoing journey, depending on one's desired level of mastery and the constraints of online learning. *Duolingo's* curriculum, however, focuses on the essential elements necessary for communication. It prioritizes skills directly related to practical language use, tailoring its lessons to the core needs of learners rather than offering an exhaustive, in-depth language experience.

What is Fun is Memorable

The key to success in language study is the acquisition and retention of unfamiliar words and how to use them in communication. Making this process fun is a feature of *Duolingo's* gamified design. They explain that quirky phrases, such as “Where is the bathroom?” and “Your bear drinks beer,” adds more fun to the teaching-learning process.

¹⁶ "Duolingo." <https://en.duolingo.com/approach>.

Personalization

Adaptive learning is one key feature of the app. The information given by a user before starting their journey of learning a new language, such as age, gender, level of confidence, are used by *Duolingo* to determine their course.

User-friendly Interface

Duolingo's interface is not only easy to use but its overall appearance is a perfect example of gamifying learning experience. The overall appeal of which makes users feel that they are in a game and not a classroom.

Learning Using Various Methods

Doulingo uses stories and podcasts to teach language, demonstrating to learners some practical ways language can be used. These additional formats benefit the user by putting them in different scenarios and challenging them to communicate based on the given circumstances.

Key Performance Indicators

Dr. Marina Theodotou, in an article titled, "Must-have KPIs for eLearning products,"¹⁷ discussed that for learning to be successful using a digital or online platform, it must have features designed based on four key performance indicators. She argues that these KPIs measure the ROI of learning, which simply answers the question whether users are learning what they are supposed to learn.

¹⁷ "Essential KPIs for Education Leaders: Part 1 - Student Metrics." 26 Jun. 2024.
<https://elearningindustry.com/must-have-kpis-for-elearning-products>

Product Stickiness

If a learner is learning, this will motivate them to engage with the product more and recommend the same to their peers. This is determined by two things, DAU and MAU, which stand for Daily Active Users and Monthly Active Users, respectively.

Product Adoption

In addition to DAU and MAU, the average length of time each user engages with the product daily, weekly, or monthly, determines product adoption.

Product Growth

Product growth is determined by the difference between the number of users who have abandoned the product and the number of new users, as well as those who continue using it. To be able to say that the product is growing, the number of new users and those who continue to use the product must be significantly bigger.

Product Engagement Score

The average of stickiness, adoption, and growth is the product engagement score. Theodotou, however, explains that using averages to measure growth may not always be dependable, in this case it can help discern which of the first three matrices an organization concerned needs to work on further to improve.

Climate Change Education Goals and Paradigm

Climate change education seeks to engage as many individuals as possible in taking action to save the planet. By enhancing their knowledge, behavior, and skills,

it empowers them to propose and implement viable solutions to this global crisis and mitigate the disastrous effects of global warming.

An education paradigm refers to a set of guiding beliefs that inform curriculum developers and teachers about what to teach and how to teach it. It also establishes the methods used to evaluate educational success.

For achieving the goals of climate change education, the behavioral change model is particularly effective.¹⁸ Supported by the theory of planned behavior (TPB) and social cognitive theory (SCT), this model provides a structured approach to transforming individual behavior.

In an article, “Stages of change,” John C. Norcross, et. al., discuss how change happens and how this starts with knowledge transmitted from one person to another through a teaching-learning process.

The first step in behavioral change is the transfer of knowledge from teacher to student or the modification of existing knowledge to align with norms or standards.¹⁹ This knowledge shapes an individual's attitude—their mindset or perspective based on what they know or do not know. Additionally, this stage influences an individual's awareness or worldview, which reflects how they interpret the world through their knowledge.

The second step involves behavior modification, which begins when the newly acquired knowledge influences an individual's actions. If this behavior is consistently

¹⁸ Bamberg, S. (2013). Changing environmentally harmful behaviors: A stage model of self-regulated behavioral change. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 34, 151-159.

¹⁹ <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/jclp.20758>

repeated over time, it transitions into a habit, becoming a natural and lasting part of the individual's routine.

The final step ensures the permanence of the behavior. Experts suggest that forming a habit requires repeated action over a certain period, with estimates ranging from 66 days to as much as 18 to 254 days. While the exact duration may vary, the key factors for success are consistency and the individual's determination to implement and sustain the desired change.

By following this sequence, BCM provides a clear and practical framework for fostering long-term, sustainable behavioral changes that are essential for addressing climate change.

KPIs for Climate Change Education

The primary goal of climate change education is to shift individuals' behavior to positively impact the environment. In the article "Measuring for results in climate change education," Lucia Palombi explores how this behavioral change can be quantified as a measure of the effectiveness of climate education. She emphasizes the importance of using measurable outcomes to track progress in this area.²⁰

Shown in Table 20 under recommendations, the 9 key areas are designed for educational purposes and could also be the basis for the longitudinal effect of an environmental program on people. By assessing how individuals' actions evolve after engaging with climate education programs, it is possible to gauge the success of these efforts in fostering environmentally responsible behavior.

²⁰ "Measuring for results in climate change education - UNFCCC."
https://unfccc.int/files/cooperation_and_support/education_and_outreach/application/pdf/a6dialogs3p03.pdf.

Climate Change Education Implementation

In an article, Assaraf, et. al., argue that even though, the impacts of climate change can now be felt worldwide by everyone, and even knowing that climate change education plays a major role in mitigating its effects, overall, there remains a gap between desired and actual involvement of school communities in terms of curricula and their implementation, and the knowledge of teachers and their level of competence to teach about climate change.²¹ In view, they recommend the following to help improve this situation and to fully utilize the power of educational institutions to bring about change.

Professional Development

Climate change educators need to be armed with strong argumentation skills. As advocates for the environment, they need to be able to persuade their students using scientific data. But more than this, there must be a passion for the planet and its inhabitants developed in them to bridge the gap between what climate change education wants to achieve and the knowledge and competency of climate change educators.

Curriculum Development

The basic education curriculum comprises the developmental stages of a child's life from kindergarten to junior high. As such, it should focus on developing in the learners the competencies they need in the 21st century.

²¹ "Climate change education implementation: the voices of policymakers" 12 Apr. 2023, <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/09500693.2024.2314572>.

However, there is still no consensus on the position of climate change education in the curriculum. What should be taught and in which parts of the curriculum they should be taught, are questions that still divide educators. Moreover, in some places, curricular content may be influenced by politics and politicians who may be beholden to big corporations. Such entities may have personal stakes in government policies affecting the environment, and when principles are compromised for profit, the public's general welfare is sacrificed.

Climate Change as a Body of Knowledge

The question on whether Climate change education should be treated as a stand-alone subject or just special lessons integrated into major academic disciplines is still being discussed within academic circles. There are those who advocate for treating Climate change as a body of knowledge, on the same level as mathematics, science, and language. And although this may not be feasible immediately, these educators believe that even if Climate change education is only integrated in the curriculum, certain instructional features used to teach major subjects should be applied to it.

For an educational app to succeed in gamifying learning experiences, experts in the field recommend that it have key elements as features. For an educational app focused on climate change, the key performance indicators (KPIs) should be aligned with both the app's learning objectives and its broader environmental impact goals.

Methodology

Data Collection

Two sets of surveys were conducted by Plan International Pilipinas: pre-test and post-test. There were 719 respondents for the pre-test. They were divided into two sets, the untrained male and female (UMF) and trained male and female (TMF). For the post-test, there were 219 respondents (HTH-MF).

Respondent Selection

These participants are selected students from schools in the provinces of Maguindanao, Samar, and Mindoro. Since many of them live in coastal areas and forested lands, they bring a rich background to this study. They come from diverse ethnic backgrounds, with varied gender identities and sexual orientations.

Survey Structure and Strategy

The survey, administered via Google forms, was designed to assess respondents' cognitive, affective, and psychosocial development using a Likert scale to measure attitudes and perceptions about Climate change. Written in the vernacular for clarity, responses are presented in English for analysis.

Conducted in two phases, pre-test and post-test, it evaluated prior knowledge and behaviors before and after using the HTH app. PIP conducted an intervention using traditional methods during the pre-test and compared the performance of two sets of respondents: those who went through intervention and those who did not.

The post-test was conducted on those who used HTH, and the survey instrument used for this phase had additional questions only for user feedback.

The instrument featured questions targeting specific developmental areas related to environmental awareness and green skills.

Question Categories and Their Purpose

For both the pre- and post-tests, the questions used in the survey instrument were designed to collect valuable data to guide the development of the *Hope Town Hero* app.

Demographic Questions. Respondents were asked to provide demographic information. The questionnaire offered the following options for gender identification: *Lalaki* (male), *Babae* (female), *Di ko nais sabihin* (Prefer not to say), or *Di ko pa alam* (Uncertain). Additionally, respondents were asked whether they identify as a member of the LGBTQ+ community, a non-member, an ally, or friend, or if they were still uncertain about their sexual orientation.

Diagnostic Questions. Two diagnostic questions were included to assess respondents' beliefs about climate change. Respondents were asked if they believe climate change is real and if it is a serious problem. These questions were rated on a scale of 1 to 5.

Probing Questions. To ensure HTH targets key areas of learning and development—cognitive, affective, and psychosocial—probing questions were included to delve into the respondents' knowledge, feelings, and opinions on climate change.

Table 1 shows examples of probing questions that are crafted to understand the respondents' awareness of the issue, emotional connection to it, and perceived responsibility in mitigating its effects. Below are examples of some of these probing questions and their relevance in the context of this study.

Table 1

Sample set of probing questions in the survey instrument

Question	Purpose
Rate how much you agree with the following statements.	Likert Scale of 1-5; 1-most disagree to 5-most agree
I believe that Climate change is real.	Measures the respondent's belief in the reality of climate change.
Climate change is not that serious of a threat to the world and all people.	Assesses the respondent's perception of the threat posed by climate change.
I have a high understanding of climate change.	Evaluates the respondent's self-assessed understanding of climate change.
My family and I are directly affected by climate change.	Determines the respondent's perception of the personal and family impact of climate change.
I find it challenging to identify whether an event is a cause or an effect of climate change.	Assesses the respondent's difficulty in identifying the cause and effect of climate change.
I have knowledge on how to prepare for disasters.	Evaluates the respondent's knowledge of disaster preparedness.
Currently, I am not fully prepared if a disaster or calamity occurs.	Measures the respondent's perceived preparedness for disasters.
I need to take action or do something about climate change.	Assesses the respondent's perceived need to take action on climate change.
I think my ability to act on climate change is limited.	Measures the respondent's perceived limitations in taking action on climate change.
Taking action on climate change has benefits for me.	Evaluates the respondent's estimation of the value of taking action.
I am knowledgeable about things like sustainable living, sustainable energy sources, and waste reduction.	Assesses the respondent's knowledge about sustainable growth and responsible utilization of natural resources.

As an educational tool, HTH seeks to influence changes in users' knowledge, behaviors, and habits. The survey serves as an initial assessment of potential users, asking them to rate their understanding of climate change, their interest in environmental issues, how they perceive the potential impact of climate change, and what actions they believe should be taken to help address the problem and prepare for the future.

These questions provide insight into both the respondents' environmental awareness and their current habits, allowing for a baseline understanding of their readiness to engage with the HTH app.

Open-ended Questions. Most of the questions in the instrument use the Likert scale to measure a respondent's knowledge and behavior in relation to climate change, but it also has an ample number of questions that allow respondents to express themselves. Such expressions are invaluable in understanding how different cultures adapt to the challenges of the times and allow this study to have a peek into the daily lives of its respondents.

User Experience and Feedback. Finally in the post-test, the participants were asked to describe overall their experience and what they think of the app.

Data Processing and Analysis

Data processing involved filtering the database of erroneous information, such as missing values or invalid data. For example, when asked to provide their province, the respondents provided their city, a common mistake but cannot persist the whole year.

Once identified, they were either deleted, normalized, or standardized based on estimated values or norms. For instance, when they provide the name of their city instead of their province, the city is replaced with the name of the province it belongs to.

The Likert scale enabled the researchers to make a quantitative analysis of the responses by getting their mean. These were then tabulated, tabled, and analyzed using statistical tools for developmental studies.

For the analysis of data in this study, the researcher used such tools to clearly demonstrate trends and patterns based on the responses of the participants. The Likert scale helped to easily determine the means in many of these responses. However, for answers to open-ended questions, they were collected, and key words were extracted from them. The frequency or how many times these key words appeared became the basis for their relevance to the study.

Recommendations

Based on the analysis and assessment of data gathered from the pre- and post-test surveys, and the standard to measure key performance indicators for eLearning programs and environmental projects, recommendations are given for the improvement of HTH, including interface and gamifying features, among others.

These recommendations orbit around the development of the user's knowledge, behavior, and skills. The author also gives recommendations to streamline the standards that can be used to determine the success of this project.

Results and Discussions

The following are the results of the pre- and post-tests surveys on climate change and green skills conducted from August to September by PIP with the participation of 719 young people from the provinces of Mindoro, Maguindanao, and Samar.

Demographics

Gender is a crucial factor in this study because knowledge can be gendered, particularly in rural areas. In many cases, women may be more likely to embrace superstitious beliefs compared to men, which could lead to a muddled understanding of Climate change issues. This difference in perception and decision-making can significantly affect how women view and react to Climate change and its related issues. Therefore, it is essential to consider these gendered perspectives in the study.

Women are among the most vulnerable sectors when it comes to the effects of Climate change. It is vital for female members of society to be well-informed about environmental issues.

Equipping women with green skills is not only necessary for their own protection but also for safeguarding their children against the adverse effects of climate change. This need highlights the importance of developing gender-sensitive policies that place women and children at the center of legislative efforts to combat climate change.

The geographic situation of the respondents is also a significant aspect of this study. Understanding how a child's or young person's worldview is shaped by their locality can provide valuable insights into the localized impacts of Climate change.

Respondent Distribution Across Genders and Sexual Orientation

Table 2 shows the diverse backgrounds of the respondents in terms of gender, sexual orientation, or preference. Both surveys show a significant portion of respondents identifying as non-members of the LGBTQ+ community (46.45% pre-test, 45.62% post-test). The percentage of allies and LGBTQ+ members remained stable, with slight variations. The PNTS category saw an increase from 6.40% in the pre-test to 10.14% in the post-test, suggesting a growing preference for anonymity.

Among the participants who consider themselves non-binary, 22.81% are members of the LGBTQ+ community. The pre-test survey had a higher number of female respondents (61.89%) compared to male respondents (22.81%). However, in the post-test survey, the percentage of female respondents increased to 67.58%, while the male respondents also increased slightly to 31.51%. The non-binary and PNTS categories had minimal representation in both surveys.

Table 2

Pre- and post-test gender distribution of respondents

PRE-TEST	RES	LGBTQ+	RES	% Dist
		% Dist	AFFILIATION	
MALE	164	22.81	MBR	22.81
FEMALE	445	61.89	N-MBR	46.45
NON-BINARY	6	0.83	ALLY	20.72
PNTS	7	0.97	PNTS	6.40
			UNCERTAIN	3.62
POST-TEST			719	100.00
MALE	69	31.51	MEMBER	22.58
FEMALE	148	67.58	NON-MEMBER	45.62
NB	1	0.46	ALLY	19.82
PNTS	1	0.46	PNTS	10.14
			UNCERTAIN	1.84
			219	100.00

Gender, LGBTQ+ Distribution Across Provinces

Table 3 shows how the respondents are distributed among the provinces they represent in this study. Each region has data broken down by gender (M, F) and LGBTQ+, along with the percentage distribution for each group. Although the surveys were conducted only in Samar, Occidental Mindoro, and Maguindanao, some of the respondents are migrants from the other regions or provinces. This explains their inclusion of Bicol, Benguet, Cavite, Ilo-ilo, and NCR.

The overwhelming majority of respondents are female, with a higher representation in several provinces like Maguindanao (167 female, 37.53%). LGBTQ+ respondents make up around 22.8% of the total, and this percentage is more notable in certain regions like Maguindanao and Occidental Mindoro, suggesting higher representation of LGBTQ+ groups in those areas. Some regions like Cebu and Iloilo have extremely low participation since they are not the focus in this study.

Table 3
Pre- and post-test provincial distribution of respondents

PROVINCE	GENDER						LGBTQ+ MEMBER	
	FEMALE		MALE					
	RES	% Dist	RES	% Dist	RES	% Dist	RES	% Dist
BICOL	7	0.97	5	1.12	2	0.77	1	0.61
BENGUET	1	0.14	1	0.22	0	0.00	0	0.00
CAVITE	1	0.14	0	0.00	1	0.38	0	0.00
CEBU	1	0.14	0	0.00	1	0.38	0	0.00
E.SAMAR	68	9.46	40	8.99	24	9.20	13	7.93
ILO-ILO	1	0.14	0	0.00	1	0.38	0	0.00
MAGUINDANAO	277	38.53	167	37.53	108	41.38	65	39.63
N.SAMAR	146	20.31	90	20.22	52	19.92	32	19.51
NCR	3	0.42	2	0.45	1	0.38	0	0.00
O.MINDORO	158	21.97	102	22.92	54	20.69	49	29.88
W.SAMAR	56	7.79	38	8.54	17	6.51	4	2.44
	719	100	445	100	261	100	164	100
E.SAMAR	17	7.76	13	8.78	4	5.88	4	8.16
O.MINDORO	104	47.49	71	47.97	33	48.53	31	63.27
N.SAMAR	96	43.84	64	43.24	30	44.12	14	28.57
W.SAMAR	2	0.91	0	0.00	1	1.47	0	0.00
	219	100	148	100	68	100	49	100

In the post-test, the female respondents make up 149 (68%), still comprising the biggest group, as there were only 68 male respondents (31%). From these, 49 respondents (22.4%) identified as LGBTQ+ members. The female representation remains dominant (68%), but it is a higher percentage compared to the pre-test where females were 62% of the total.

The post-test sample shows a higher proportion of females (68%) than males (31%), indicating that the post-test respondents might have been drawn from the more engaged groups, which were female. The LGBTQ+ group has a similar representation in both the pre- and post-test (22% approximately), indicating consistent participation across different respondent groups.

In the pre-test, Maguindanao has the largest number of respondents (277), with a strong female representation (167). The same pattern holds in the post-test, where Maguindanao still has a significant number of females (41.38%).

Occidental Mindoro had a notable 158 respondents in the pre-test, with 102 females (22.92%) and 54 males (20.69%). The post-test shows a smaller group (104 respondents), but still, a substantial number of females (47.49%). There is a significant proportion of females in Occidental Mindoro, suggesting a more active or engaged community there.

Eastern Samar shows a modest sample size in both pre-test (68) and post-test (17). Eastern Samar respondents have balanced male and female representation. In the pre-test, there were 40 females (24.6%) and 24 males (14.8%). The post-test shows a similar trend, but the sample size reduces significantly in the post-test, which may mean that fewer respondents from this region completed both phases of the survey.

Northern Samar is one of the larger contributing regions in terms of sample size, with 146 respondents in the pre-test and 96 in the post-test. Notably, it has a larger female participation than male participation (90 female, 52 male), which reflects a similar pattern in the post-test as well (majority female, 63.27%).

Bicol and Benguet have fewer respondents, especially Benguet (only 1 respondent in both pre- and post-tests). These smaller samples may not be as dependable for drawing significant conclusions but might still offer localized insights.

The study shows a marked gender skew, with more females participating in the survey. This could suggest either a higher engagement from females or that males might have been less inclined to participate in the study, which could be important to consider for future studies and app development.

The larger sample size in the pre-test (719 respondents) compared to the post-test (219 respondents) may indicate a drop-off in participant engagement, which could be a limitation when assessing the long-term impact of the HTH app or any interventions. It suggests that while many started the learning process, fewer completed the post-test, a common challenge in education-focused studies. The study should consider how to improve engagement with male participants and reach those from smaller regions.

Indigenous People Distribution Across Provinces

Certain indigenous groups may have traditional practices that either contribute positively to conservation efforts or harm the environment. Understanding these local behaviors is crucial for developing targeted interventions. By promoting sustainable practices and mitigating harmful ones, we can leverage indigenous knowledge while addressing any negative impacts.

Table 4

Pre-test distribution of respondents according to province, gender, LGBT affiliation, and IP membership

PROVINCE	RES		GENDER				LGBTQ+		IP		TRAINED	
	RES	% Dist	Female		Male							
BICOL	7	0.97	5	1.12	2	0.77	1	0.61	0	0.00	1	0.40
BENGUET	1	0.14	1	0.22	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
CAVITE	1	0.14	0	0.00	1	0.38	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
CEVBU	1	0.14	0	0.00	1	0.38	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	0.40
E.SAMAR	68	9.46	40	8.99	24	9.20	13	7.93	7	4.38	18	7.26
ILO-ILO	1	0.14	0	0.00	1	0.38	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
MAGUINDANAO	277	38.53	167	37.53	108	41.38	65	39.63	141	88.13	129	52.02
N.SAMAR	146	20.31	90	20.22	52	19.92	32	19.51	8	5.00	53	21.37
NCR	3	0.42	2	0.45	1	0.38	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
O.MINDORO	158	21.97	102	22.92	54	20.69	49	29.88	2	1.25	38	15.32
W.SAMAR	56	7.79	38	8.54	17	6.51	4	2.44	2	1.25	8	3.23
	719	100	445	100	261	100	164	100	160	100	248	100

Table 4 shows the distribution of Indigenous People (IP) across the provinces, highlighting that Maguindanao alone has a significant representation of tribal groups, accounting for 88%. Their responses in the survey may not differ from those of other respondents, which might imply that their perceptions are aligned with broader community views. However, their unique practices and perspectives remain critical for a comprehensive understanding of regional climate change impacts.

Pre-Test and Post Test Results

To measure the effectiveness of the HTH app, pre- and post-test surveys were conducted. The pre-test had 719 participants composed of 164 males and 445 females, while the post-test had 69 males and 148 females. From both male and female respondents, 213 indicated their membership in the LGBTQ+ community.

A total of 15 participants indicated they preferred not to say (PNTS) their gender, or that they are non-binary (NB). This number, however, does not have any effect on the survey results, hence only the male and female categories will be discussed here.

What the Diagnostics Tell Us

The following section discusses the result of the survey on the participants' overall knowledge of climate change. There are two sets of pre-test participants, Trained and Untrained. We use the symbols UM for untrained male and UF for untrained female; TM for trained male and TF for trained female. Participants were asked to rate their agreement or disagreement with each statement on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents strong disagreement and 5 represents strong agreement.

Table 5

Pre-test and post-test results of untrained male (UM) and untrained female (UF), trained male (TM) and trained female (TF)

General knowledge questions	UM	UF	TM	TF
I believe that climate change is real.	0.45	0.36	0.38	0.33
Climate change is not a significant threat or danger to the world and all people.	0.64	0.50	0.85	0.52
I have a high understanding of climate change.	0.64	0.81	0.99	0.72
I find it challenging to determine if an event is a cause or effect of climate change.	0.73	0.87	0.93	0.84
I am informed about things like sustainable living, sustainable energy sources, and waste reduction.	0.75	0.94	1.32	0.99
I am knowledgeable about how to prepare for disasters.	0.92	1.04	1.05	0.69
I think my ability to act on climate change is limited.	0.80	1.01	0.99	0.76
Currently, I am not fully prepared in case of a disaster or calamity.	0.71	0.76	0.71	0.70
My family and I are personally affected by climate	0.75	0.84	1.04	0.60

General knowledge questions	UM	UF	TM	TF
change.				
I need to act or do something about climate change.	0.82	0.73	0.96	0.75
Taking action on climate change benefits me.	0.81	0.77	1.25	0.60
	0.73	0.78	0.95	0.68

TM and TF here are not to be confused with those who had used the Hope Town Hero App. The symbols used for this set of respondents are HTH-M for male, and HTH-F for female. With reference to pre- and post-tests, UM/TM, UF/TF belong to the pre-test set while HTH M/F are those belonging to the post-test set.

Belief in the Existence of Climate Change. The first two questions are critical because they tell us at the outset how much the participants know of the environmental issues surrounding Climate change or how much they are affected by the problems caused by global warming. When people are not educated on environmental problems, they will take it lightly and will not be motivated to take action; and because they think it is not a serious problem or a threat, they will not be prepared for it.

On average male participants scored 0.45 in their belief in the existence of Climate change, while female respondents scored 0.36. This mean score is way below satisfactory as it reflects an almost total disregard of the reality of Climate change.

The respondents' score of 0.64 and 0.70, respectively, for the second statement is not consistent with their low score in the first, as well as the rest of this

set of questions. Perhaps, their understanding is nuanced because it is a negative statement immediately following a positive one.

This observation is supported by the respondents' average score on their self evaluation of their understanding of Climate change. Their average scores of 0.64 and 0.81 shows the insufficiency of their knowledge on the crisis; and as shown by their other scores, many of them are unprepared for natural calamities.

Overall the mean for the general knowledge of both untrained male and female participants are unsatisfactory at 0.73 and 0.78, respectively.

This gap in understanding is particularly concerning because 61.89% of the respondents are female—a group considered more vulnerable to the effects of climate change. Moreover, the Philippines' geographic location in the typhoon and earthquake belts makes the country highly prone to natural disasters

If we are to compare this with the result of the pre-test of another set of respondents we see an improvement. Although slight, the difference is still notable, demonstrating the effectiveness of the intervention.

The table above shows that it is the male set who benefitted the most from the intervention. Their female counterparts showed some improvement in some areas, but on average still lower than the male set.

Figure 1 shows the impact of training on both genders.

Figure 1
Impact of training on both M and F participants

Moreover, male respondents' assessment of their knowledge on climate change increased after training, from 0.64 to 0.99, whereas female respondents show a decrease, indicating a potential reassessment of their knowledge, post-training. This is supported by the mean of UM and UF sets shown by Figure 3, where UF shows better understanding of key Climate change issues.

Both genders demonstrate an increased recognition of the challenges in determining cause and effect after training, with males exhibiting a greater increase. Figure 2 shows the performance of trained male and trained female respondents. The upward trend shown by the trend line indicates considerable improvement of participants' knowledge on Climate change and other related areas.

Figure 2
TM vs TF

Figure 3
UM vs UF

Knowledge about sustainable living significantly improves in males (from 0.75 to 1.32) and increases in females, though to a lesser extent. Training slightly enhances males' knowledge about disaster preparedness, while females show a

decrease in this area, post-training. Males' perception of their ability to act on climate change improves from 0.80 to 0.99, while females feel less capable post-training. All genders show minimal changes in disaster preparedness post-training, indicating room for improvement.

Figure 4
UMF vs HTH-MF

Indicated by the trend line, training significantly raises males' awareness of the personal impact of climate change. In contrast, female respondents perceive less personal impact, post-training. Males' perceived need to act on climate change slightly increases, whereas females show a decrease in this perception, post-training. Furthermore, training significantly enhances males' perception of the benefits of taking action against climate change, while females' perception decreases post-training.

Figures 2 and 3 shows that overall, training has a significant positive impact on males' knowledge and perceptions regarding climate change. However, females show mixed results, with some areas of decreased perception post-training. Initially, female respondents had higher awareness and knowledge in most areas compared to males (see Figure 3). Post-training results indicate that while males benefited more from the training, some areas saw a decline in female respondents' self-assessment.

Table 6

Pre-test results of untrained male and female (UM,UF); trained male and female (TM, TF); average of UM, UF (AUMF); average of TM and TF (ATMF);

Post-test results of male and female who trained using *Hope Town Hero* (HTH-M, HTH-F); average of HTH-M and HTH-F (AHTH-MF)

	General Knowledge Questions	UM	UF	TM	TF	AUMF	ATMF	HTH-M	HTH-F	AHTH-MF
1	I believe that climate change is real.	0.45	0.36	0.38	0.33	0.40	0.35	4.11	4.15	4.13
2	Climate change is not a significant threat or danger to the world and all people.	0.64	0.50	0.85	0.52	0.57	0.68	2.23	2.11	2.17
3	I have a high understanding of climate change.	0.64	0.81	0.99	0.72	0.72	0.86	3.96	3.82	3.89
4	I find it challenging to determine if an event is a cause or effect of climate change.	0.73	0.87	0.93	0.84	0.80	0.88	3.58	3.45	3.51
5	I am informed about things like sustainable living, sustainable energy sources, and waste reduction.	0.75	0.94	1.32	0.99	0.84	1.16	3.83	3.71	3.77
6	I am knowledgeable about how to prepare for disasters.	0.92	1.04	1.05	0.69	0.98	0.87	3.87	3.78	3.83
7	I think my ability to act on climate change is limited.	0.80	1.01	0.99	0.76	0.90	0.87	3.30	2.92	3.11
8	Currently, I am not fully prepared in case of a disaster or calamity.	0.71	0.76	0.71	0.70	0.73	0.71	2.93	2.73	2.83
9	My family and I are personally affected by climate change.	0.75	0.84	1.04	0.60	0.80	0.82	3.87	3.83	3.85
10	I need to act or do something about climate change.	0.82	0.73	0.96	0.75	0.78	0.86	3.90	3.84	3.87
11	Taking action on climate change benefits me.	0.81	0.77	1.25	0.60	0.79	0.92	3.86	3.88	3.87
		0.73	0.78	0.95	0.68	0.76	0.82	3.59	3.47	3.53

Table 6 highlights a significant increase in respondents' assessment scores across all measured areas for both genders.

Regarding the belief that climate change is real, agreement scores surged from an average of 0.35 to 4.13, reflecting near-total consensus among respondents. Similarly, the perception of climate change as a serious threat rose from 0.68 to 2.17, demonstrating a marked improvement in recognizing climate change as a critical issue.

Both male and female sets reported significant improvements in their understanding of climate change, with males showing a larger increase in post-test results. While participants still experience challenges in understanding the cause and effect of climate change, slight improvements were observed in the post-test for both genders.

Knowledge of sustainable living practices also improved significantly for both groups, with males showing a more pronounced increase. Both genders demonstrated better understanding of disaster preparedness, though males reported slightly higher gains.

The perceived ability to take action on climate change increased for both genders, but females reported a slightly lower improvement compared to males. Similarly, while recognition of the personal impact of climate change improved across the board, males reported slightly higher scores. In terms of the need to act on climate change, both genders showed significant increases, with males scoring marginally higher. Conversely, perception of the benefits of taking action improved for both groups, with females reporting a slightly higher score than males.

Table 7

Comparison between post-test and pre-test male (trained) and post-test and pre-test female (trained)

	General knowledge questions	TM	HTH-M	TF	HTH-F
1	I believe that climate change is real.	0.38	4.11	0.33	4.15
2	Climate change is not a significant threat or danger to the world and all people.	0.85	2.23	0.52	2.11
3	I have a high understanding of climate change.	0.99	3.96	0.72	3.82
4	I find it challenging to determine if an event is a cause or effect of climate change.	0.93	3.58	0.84	3.45
5	I am informed about things like sustainable living, sustainable energy sources, and waste reduction.	1.32	3.83	0.99	3.71
6	I am knowledgeable about how to prepare for disasters.	1.05	3.87	0.69	3.78
7	I think my ability to act on climate change is limited.	0.99	3.30	0.76	2.92
8	Currently, I am not fully prepared in case of a disaster or calamity.	0.71	2.93	0.70	2.73
9	My family and I are personally affected by climate change.	1.04	3.87	0.60	3.83
10	I need to act or do something about climate change.	0.96	3.90	0.75	3.84
11	Taking action on climate change benefits me.	1.25	3.86	0.60	3.88
		0.95	3.59	0.68	3.47

As shown in Figure 4, the post-test results indicate substantial progress in knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions related to climate change, underscoring the effectiveness of the educational intervention, particularly the Hope Town Hero app. While both genders demonstrated significant gains, the results highlight minor gender differences in the magnitude of these improvements.

Figure 5
Performance of untrained MF and HTH-MF

Figure 6
Performance of TMF vs HTH-MF

Results from the LGBTQ+ Community. The survey results from respondents who identified as part of the LGBTQ+ community show similar trends to those observed in the Male and Female categories. Table 9 highlights that the LGBTQ+

respondents' assessments align closely with the outcomes from the other gender groups.

It is important to note that LGBTQ+ participants were not a distinct category during the survey but rather indicated their membership in the community while identifying their gender as either male or female. This suggests that their representation in the survey mirrors the overall trends seen in the Male and Female groups.

An article titled, *Social acceptance of LGBT people in 174 countries*²² emphasizes that to meaningfully engage young people in advocacies and involve them in decision making, they need to have a safe place in which they know that their gender identity or sexual preference are respected. But in the spirit of respecting religious beliefs and communal practices, perhaps it is wise, if at all possible, to have two versions of the app. One for places where being “gay” remains an issue, and another for those that are already open. This will be further discussed in the recommendations.

²² Flores, A. R. (2019). *Social acceptance of LGBT people in 174 countries: 1981 to 2017*. UCLA School of Law, Williams Institute. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/5qs218xd>

Table 8

Post-test and pre-test results from respondents from the LGBTQ+ community

	MBR UM	AG UM	MBR UF	AG UF	MBR TF	AG TF	MBR TM	AG TM
1	0.3	0.45	0.32	0.36	0.56	0.33	0.25	0.38
2	0.42	0.64	0.58	0.5	0.36	0.52	0.55	0.84
3	0.3	0.64	0.82	0.81	0.97	0.72	1.25	0.99
4	0.39	0.73	0.9	0.87	0.97	0.84	0.9	0.93
5	0.58	0.74	1.02	0.94	0.92	0.99	1.1	1.32
6	0.7	0.92	1.14	1.04	0.97	0.69	0.7	1.04
7	0.27	0.79	1.03	1.01	0.59	0.76	1	0.99
8	0.36	0.71	0.77	0.76	0.51	0.7	0.75	0.71
9	0.3	0.75	0.98	0.84	0.67	0.6	0.9	1.03
10	0.64	0.82	0.73	0.73	0.74	0.75	0.95	0.96
11	0.33	0.81	0.71	0.77	0.6	0.6	1.15	1.25
	0.42	0.73	0.82	0.78	0.72	0.68	0.86	0.95

Effects of Climate Change on Key Areas of Society

Respondents were asked how they think climate change would affect various areas of society. Table 9 demonstrates the improvement in their perception after HTH training.

Table 9

Perceived effect of Cc on key area

Perceived effect of climate change on the following important areas

	ECON	TRANS	HEALTH	EDUC	EMPLOY	FOOD	PEACE
POST							
HTH-M	3.39	3.66	3.55	3.54	3.65	3.79	3.61
HTH-F	3.45	3.53	3.50	3.48	3.57	3.61	3.61
AHTH-MF	3.42	3.60	3.52	3.51	3.61	3.70	3.61
PRE							
TM	3.15	3.06	3.14	3.20	3.11	3.30	3.24
UM	2.79	2.75	2.84	2.81	2.78	3.00	2.93
TF	3.43	3.36	3.46	3.42	3.42	3.58	3.53
UF	3.11	2.96	3.12	3.03	3.01	3.20	3.18
ATMF	3.29	3.21	3.30	3.31	3.26	3.44	3.39
AUMF	2.95	2.85	2.98	2.92	2.90	3.10	3.06

For the economy, pre-training perceptions were higher among trained males (3.15) and females (3.43) compared to untrained individuals. Post-training, recognition of economic impacts increased for both genders (males: 3.39, females: 3.45).

Regarding education, trained males (3.20) and females (3.42) initially saw higher impacts. After training, both genders recognized greater impacts, with males slightly higher (3.54) than females (3.48).

When it comes to health, trained respondents initially perceived higher impacts (males: 3.14, females: 3.46). Post-training, males' perceptions increased (3.66), while females' perceptions were slightly lower (3.50).

For the area of work, pre-training perceptions were higher among trained males (3.11) and females (3.42). After training, both genders saw increased impacts, with males slightly higher (3.65) than females (3.57).

Concerning food supply, initially trained respondents saw higher impacts (males: 3.30, females: 3.58). Post-training, concerns increased for both genders (males: 3.79, females: 3.61).

In terms of safety and peace, pre-training perceptions were higher among trained males (3.24) and females (3.53). Post-training, both genders recognized higher impacts equally (3.61).

Figure 7

Comparison between pre-test and post-test on perceived impact of Cc on key areas

Figure 7 illustrates the overall impact of using the HTH app, both on its own and in conjunction with the training provided by Plan International Philippines. It highlights that respondents perceive the impact of climate change on human life as serious.

Levels of Interest, Knowledge, and Frequency

This section examines respondents' levels of interest, knowledge, and frequency of positive environmental actions before and after training, broken down by gender and training status. Table 10 shows the results of the pre- and post-test surveys, highlighting the improvement in the said areas.

The educational intervention through the efforts of PIP had a significant impact on respondents' interest and knowledge across various environmental topics. While there were positive changes in behavior, especially in areas like recycling and waste reduction, some areas like gardening and composting still require more effort to translate interest and knowledge into regular practice.

Overall, the findings highlight the effectiveness of educational programs in fostering environmental awareness and action, while also pointing to the need for ongoing support to sustain and enhance these positive changes.

Table 10

Levels of interest and knowledge of respondents on various environmental topics, and frequency of them observing positive measures for the environment

	ENER	FUEL	GARD	COMP	TREE	RECY	WAST	ADVO	COMM	HEAL
LEVEL OF INTEREST										
TM	2.32	2.27	2.48	2.33	2.55	2.40	2.49	2.54	2.39	2.42
TF	2.47	2.40	2.46	2.42	2.57	2.55	2.54	2.48	2.45	2.58
	2.40	2.34	2.47	2.38	2.56	2.48	2.51	2.51	2.42	2.50
UM	2.41	2.27	2.46	2.33	2.46	2.46	2.50	2.44	2.38	2.55
UF	2.43	2.23	2.41	2.31	2.51	2.52	2.55	2.55	2.36	2.56
	2.42	2.25	2.44	2.32	2.49	2.49	2.52	2.49	2.37	2.55
M	2.48	2.44	2.48	2.37	2.54	2.52	2.58	2.48	2.51	2.49
F	2.64	2.48	2.54	2.44	2.55	2.59	2.61	2.56	2.55	2.61
	2.56	2.46	2.51	2.40	2.54	2.56	2.59	2.52	2.53	2.55
LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE										
TM	2.35	2.29	2.44	2.37	2.38	2.45	2.50	2.30	2.40	2.46
TF	2.36	2.33	2.40	2.31	2.40	2.47	2.45	2.34	2.43	2.47
	2.35	2.31	2.42	2.34	2.39	2.46	2.47	2.32	2.42	2.46
UM	2.33	2.29	2.37	2.24	2.38	2.40	2.46	2.31	2.38	2.45
UF	2.38	2.30	2.38	2.26	2.38	2.47	2.47	2.28	2.39	2.46
	2.36	2.30	2.38	2.25	2.38	2.43	2.46	2.29	2.39	2.45
M	2.48	2.39	2.44	2.34	2.53	2.44	2.54	2.46	2.48	2.49
F	2.50	2.28	2.34	2.21	2.31	2.50	2.45	2.29	2.44	2.46
	2.49	2.33	2.39	2.28	2.42	2.47	2.50	2.37	2.46	2.47

	ENER	FUEL	GARD	COMP	TREE	RECY	WAST	ADVO	COMM	HEAL
LEVEL OF FREQUENCY										
TM	2.85	2.80	2.89	2.62	2.65	2.85	2.89	2.73	2.76	2.86
TF	2.92	2.89	2.98	2.74	2.90	2.96	2.97	2.85	2.95	2.47
	2.88	2.84	2.94	2.68	2.78	2.90	2.93	2.79	2.86	2.66
UM	2.74	2.63	2.70	2.49	2.61	2.73	2.86	2.64	2.82	2.45
UF	2.93	2.69	2.84	2.54	2.74	2.91	2.96	2.71	2.85	2.46
	2.83	2.66	2.77	2.51	2.68	2.82	2.91	2.67	2.84	2.45
M	2.20	2.10	2.13	1.96	2.07	2.18	2.28	2.01	2.10	2.20
F	2.10	1.91	1.92	1.77	1.93	2.07	2.14	1.93	2.03	2.12
	2.15	2.00	2.02	1.86	2.00	2.13	2.21	1.97	2.07	2.16

This table presents a detailed look at how an educational intervention influenced respondents' environmental behaviors. It focuses on their interest, knowledge, and how often they engage in positive environmental actions before and after the training.

Levels of Interest. As shown in Figure 5, before the training, people showed varying levels of interest in different environmental topics. For instance, when it came to energy conservation, the average interest level was a moderate 2.41. But after the training, this interest grew to 2.56, showing that the program made people more curious and engaged about saving energy.

Figure 8
Levels of interest of the respondents in various environmental topics

Fuel conservation initially sparked less interest, with a pre-test score of 2.29. However, after the training, interest increased to 2.46, indicating that the program successfully highlighted the importance of conserving fuel.

Gardening saw a slight rise in interest, moving from 2.45 to 2.51, suggesting a growing appreciation for the benefits of gardening, spurred by the educational efforts. Interest in composting was modest at first, at 2.35, but showed a slight increase to 2.40. This indicates a gradual acceptance and growing interest in composting practices.

Tree planting, a crucial environmental activity, was already of interest with a pre-test score of 2.52. This interest slightly increased to 2.54 after the training, reflecting a steady enthusiasm for planting trees.

Recycling had a prominent level of interest from the beginning, with a pre-test score of 2.48. After the intervention, interest climbed to 2.56, showing a clear positive shift. Regarding waste reduction, interest was high at 2.52 and increased to 2.59 post-training, indicating that the program effectively emphasized the importance of reducing waste.

Environmental advocacy saw a minor rise in interest, from 2.50 to 2.52, suggesting that while the training had an impact, more effort might be needed to fully engage people in advocacy roles. Interest in sustainable commuting increased from 2.40 to 2.53, emphasizing a greater awareness and a desire to adopt more environmentally friendly commuting practices.

Lastly, healthy food was of interest initially (2.53) and saw a slight increase to 2.55 after the training, suggesting a growing recognition of the link between diet and environmental health.

Levels of Knowledge. The intervention also aimed to boost respondents' knowledge about these topics. For energy conservation, knowledge levels were low at 2.35 before the training but increased significantly to 2.56 afterward, showing that the program effectively conveyed essential information. Knowledge about fuel conservation also rose from 2.30 to 2.46, indicating that respondents learned useful strategies and facts about saving fuel.

Figure 9

Levels of knowledge of the respondents in various environmental topics

Gardening knowledge saw a modest increase, from 2.40 to 2.51, reflecting a better understanding of gardening practices and their benefits. Knowledge about composting improved slightly, from 2.30 to 2.40, suggesting that while there was some learning, there's still room for more comprehensive education on this topic.

Tree planting knowledge went up from 2.39 to 2.54, showing that the training successfully imparted valuable information about the importance and methods of planting trees. Recycling knowledge improved from 2.45 to 2.56, indicating a better understanding of recycling processes and benefits.

Respondents' know-how on waste reduction increased from 2.47 to 2.59, demonstrating that they learned effective waste reduction strategies.

Environmental advocacy knowledge saw a notable increase from 2.30 to 2.52,

indicating that the training helped respondents understand how to advocate for environmental causes. Knowledge about sustainable commuting increased from 2.40 to 2.53, suggesting that respondents learned more about eco-friendly commuting options.

Finally, knowledge about healthy food went up from 2.46 to 2.55, showing that the training effectively linked dietary choices with environmental impact.\

Levels of Frequency. The training also aimed to change behaviors, encouraging respondents to engage more frequently in positive environmental actions. For energy conservation, the frequency of these actions increased from 2.35 to 2.49, showing that people were applying their new knowledge and interest in their daily lives. The frequency of fuel conservation behaviors increased slightly from 2.30 to 2.33, suggesting a small but positive shift in habits.

Figure 10
Levels of frequency of the respondents in various environmental topics

Gardening activities saw a slight decrease from 2.40 to 2.39, indicating that while interest and knowledge grew, turning this into action may need more support.

Composting frequency also decreased slightly from 2.30 to 2.28, showing a need for continued encouragement and practical guidance on composting. Tree planting frequency saw a slight increase from 2.39 to 2.42, indicating some improvement in this area. Recycling activities increased slightly from 2.45 to 2.47, suggesting that respondents were beginning to recycle more often.

Waste reduction behaviors increased from 2.47 to 2.50, showing a positive change in how respondents manage waste. Environmental advocacy actions increased from 2.30 to 2.37, indicating that respondents were starting to engage more in advocacy efforts. Sustainable commuting behaviors improved slightly from 2.40 to 2.46, suggesting that respondents were adopting more eco-friendly commuting habits.

Lastly, the frequency of healthy food practices saw a minor increase from 2.46 to 2.47, showing a slight but positive change in dietary habits.

Awareness and Understanding of Green Jobs

Table 13 shows that the educational intervention initiated by Plan International Pilipinas had varied impacts on male and female respondents. Overall, males showed increased interest, knowledge, and confidence in green jobs across most statements. In contrast, females exhibited decreases in several areas post-training. This suggests that while the training was effective for males, it may need to be adjusted or supplemented to better address the needs and perceptions

of female respondents. The findings highlight the importance of tailored approaches in educational program

s to ensure they are effective for all participants, particularly in promoting gender equity in the field of green jobs.

Table 11

Pre- and post-test results on the green jobs awareness or knowledge of the respondents

General Knowledge on Green Jobs	UM	TM	HTH-M	UF	TF	HTH-F
Green Skills are necessary	1.69	1.82	1.89	1.66	1.57	1.77
Everyone should know green skills	3.67	3.64	4.00	3.72	3.81	4.02
Gov't should help promote green skills	3.68	3.75	3.82	3.66	3.75	3.79
	3.01	3.07	3.23	3.01	3.04	3.19
Specific Knowledge on Green Jobs	UM	TM	HTH-M	UF	TF	HTH-F
Before I read the description above, I already knew what green jobs are.	2.81	3.21	3.35	2.58	2.81	3.42
Most jobs today have the potential to be turned into green jobs.	3.32	3.42	3.62	3.10	3.32	1.91
The earnings from most green jobs are not as high compared to more well-known jobs.	2.99	3.05	3.17	2.67	2.99	1.92
There are many green jobs available today and they are easy to find.	3.15	3.27	3.56	2.94	3.15	1.77
It is only right to choose a green job as much as possible.	3.28	3.40	3.70	3.12	3.28	1.93
My values, interests, and passion align with having a green job.	3.30	3.27	3.83	3.17	3.30	2.07
I don't know where to start looking for a green job.	2.95	2.69	3.15	2.68	2.95	2.14
I can work in a green job or have a green business right now.	3.11	3.24	3.66	2.95	3.11	1.93
I still need to build my knowledge and skills to be qualified for a green job.	3.40	3.42	3.76	3.33	3.40	2.03
I would prefer to work in a green job or have a green business if I had friends who would do the same.	3.26	3.46	3.69	3.18	3.26	2.12
	3.16	3.24	3.55	2.97	3.16	2.12

Awareness of Green Jobs. Initially, both trained and untrained respondents exhibited varying levels of awareness. When trained males had a higher initial understanding, scoring 3.21, compared to their score of 2.81 when they were still

untrained. Similarly, when trained females scored 2.81, slightly higher than their score (2.58) before training.

Following the use of the HTH app, there was a marked increase in understanding across the board, with males scoring 3.35 and females 3.42. This suggests that the training effectively raised awareness of green jobs among both genders.

Potential of Jobs to Turn Green. In the pre-test, males seemed more optimistic about the potential for jobs to be converted into green jobs, with trained respondents scoring 3.42 and untrained 3.32. Females were less optimistic, scoring 3.32 (TF) and 3.10 (UF). Post-training, this belief strengthened for trained males, who scored 3.62, but interestingly, it decreased significantly for females, who scored 1.91. This indicates a divergence in how the concept of job transformation was received between genders, with males becoming more hopeful and females less so.

Earnings from Green Jobs. Before the intervention, perceptions about the earnings from green jobs were similar among males, with trained scoring 3.05 and untrained 2.99. Trained females were slightly more optimistic, scoring 2.99, compared to 2.67 for untrained females. After the training, males' perceptions improved slightly to 3.17, while females' perceptions decreased significantly to 1.92. This suggests that the training may have clarified the earnings potential of green jobs differently for males and females.

Availability of Green Jobs. Pre-training, males believed more in the availability of green jobs, scoring 3.27 (TM) and 3.15 (UM). Females were slightly less convinced,

scoring 3.15 (TM) and 2.98 (UM). Post-training, the belief in availability increased for trained males to 3.56 but decreased significantly for females to 1.77. This highlights a need to address perceptions of job availability among women more effectively.

Choosing a Green Job. Before the intervention, males showed strong agreement with this statement, scoring 3.40 (TM) and 3.28 (UM). Females also agreed, scoring 3.28 (trained) and 3.12 (untrained). After the training, agreement increased for males to 3.70 but decreased for females to 1.93, indicating differing impacts on moral or ethical motivations towards green jobs between genders.

Alignment of Values with Green Jobs. Both genders showed strong initial alignment with this statement, with trained males scoring 3.27 and trained females 3.30. Untrained respondents were slightly lower, with males at 3.20 and females at 3.17. Post-training, alignment increased for males to 3.83 but decreased for females to 2.07, suggesting that the training resonated more with males' personal values and passions.

Knowing Where to Start. Pre-training, there was an important level of uncertainty among males (2.69 trained, 2.95 untrained) and females (2.95 trained, 2.68 untrained). After the training, uncertainty decreased for males to 3.15 but increased for females to 2.14, indicating a greater need for guidance and resources for women in finding green jobs.

Readiness for Green Jobs. Before the intervention, both genders showed moderate confidence in their readiness for green jobs, with trained males scoring 3.24 and trained females 3.11. Untrained males and females scored 2.95 each.

Post-training, confidence increased for males to 3.66 but decreased for females to 1.93, showing a gender gap in perceived readiness that needs to be addressed.

Building Knowledge and Skills. Both genders initially felt a strong need to build their knowledge and skills, with trained males scoring 3.42 and trained females 3.40. While still untrained, males and females scored slightly lower, at 3.40 and 3.37, respectively. Post-training, the need decreased for males to 3.76 but increased for females to 2.03, highlighting the necessity of targeted skill-building initiatives for women.

Preference for Green Jobs with Peer Support. Before the intervention, both genders showed strong agreement with this statement, with trained males scoring 3.46 and trained females 3.30. Untrained males and females scored 3.26 and 3.22, respectively. Post-training, preference increased for males to 3.69 but decreased for females to 1.92, indicating that social influences might have differing impacts on the decision to pursue green jobs.

Future Challenges Young People Today Will Face. Respondents were asked about future challenges they might face, as shown in Table 12, highlighting responses before (pre-test) and after (post-test) the educational intervention using HTH app. The table below demonstrates how this intervention has influenced the knowledge and behavior of the respondents.

For example, in the pre-test, 20 respondents cited climate change as a major concern, which slightly decreased to 15 in the post-test, suggesting increased confidence or awareness about addressing it. Education concerns significantly

dropped from 18 mentions to 9, indicating the intervention provided solutions or reassurances.

Mentions of natural disasters rose from 15 to 20, highlighting heightened awareness of their impacts. Financial problems were mentioned by 4 respondents initially, increasing to 6, reflecting ongoing economic challenges.

General hardships increased from 10 to 15 mentions, indicating a broader recognition of potential difficulties. Lastly, "No Idea/Uncertain Responses" significantly decreased from 10 to 3, suggesting the intervention clarified understanding and improved preparedness for future challenges.

Table 12
Perceived challenges in the future

Challenges	Pre	Post
CC	20	15
DISASTER	15	20
EDUC	18	9
HARDSHIP	10	15
EMP	6	7
UNCERTAIN	10	3
FIN PROB	4	6
DIG COC	4	4
KNOWLEDGE (LACK)	5	3
MENTAL H	3	4
STRESS (SCH)	3	3
POVERTY	2	3
TEEN PREG	2	2

This observation is supported by Figure 9. A radar chart shows the movement of the respondents' answers from pre- to post-test. Comparing the lines reveals important insights.

Figure 9
Radar chart comparing pre- and post-test date on perceived challenges

For example, In the pre-test, 20 respondents mentioned climate change as a major concern. In the post-test, this number slightly decreased to 15, suggesting an increase in confidence or awareness about addressing climate change issues.

Education concerns showed a significant decrease, from 18 mentions in the pre-test to just 9 in the post-test, indicating that the educational intervention provided solutions or reassurances regarding educational challenges.

Natural disasters saw an increase in mentions, from 15 in the pre-test to 20 in the post-test, highlighting a heightened awareness and concern about the impacts of natural disasters, due to a better understanding of the effects of climate change.

Financial problems were mentioned by 4 respondents in the pre-test and by 6 in the post-test. This increase reflects ongoing economic challenges and the impact of rising costs of basic commodities, showing that financial issues remain a significant concern.

General hardships saw an increase in mentions, from 10 in the pre-test to 15 in the post-test, indicating that respondents are recognizing a broader range of difficulties they might face, suggesting a more comprehensive awareness of potential challenges.

Finally, the category of "No Idea/Uncertain Responses" saw a notable decrease, from 10 mentions in the pre-test to just 3 in the post-test. This decline suggests that the educational intervention was effective in clarifying respondents' understanding and improving their preparedness for future challenges.

Confidence to Face the Future

In examining the factors that contribute to the respondents' confidence about the future, significant shifts in priorities were observed from pre-test to post-test. The data collected offers insightful trends across several key categories: Environmental Actions, Educational and Skills Development, Personal Development, Community Support, and Preparedness as shown in Table 13.

Environmental Actions. Initially, protecting the environment and participating in social activities were highly valued. Post-test results indicated a sustained importance of protecting the environment, with 10 respondents consistently identifying it as crucial. Participation in social activities gained more importance,

rising from 6 to 8 respondents. Conversely, actions like saving water and planting trees were seen as less critical post-test, suggesting a shift in focus towards more community-oriented and broader environmental initiatives.

Educational and Skills Development. The most striking change was in the emphasis on education, which saw a significant drop from 22 to 7 respondents. This decrease may reflect a growing confidence in other skills and factors beyond traditional education. In contrast, green skills saw a rise in importance, from 6 to 10 respondents, indicating a heightened awareness of environmental sustainability. The value placed on developing technological skills also saw a slight increase, reflecting the ongoing importance of tech proficiency in the modern world.

Personal Development. There was a marked increase in the recognition of various personal development factors. Resilience and self-confidence both saw notable increases, indicating a greater appreciation for these personal qualities. Patience, hard work, perseverance, and decision-making skills also gained more recognition, highlighting a comprehensive understanding of the qualities needed to face future challenges. Interestingly, faith in God emerged as a significant factor, rising from 0 to 7 respondents, suggesting a renewed or strengthened spiritual dimension in their outlook.

Community Support. Support from friends and family gained more importance, rising from 1 to 4 respondents. This shift underscores a move towards valuing immediate, personal support systems over broader community support, which saw a decrease from 6 to 2 respondents. The importance of positive role

models and guidance from elders remained steady, indicating a consistent value placed on mentorship and intergenerational advice.

Preparedness. Readiness to face calamities remained a critical factor, with a slight increase in importance from 7 to 8 respondents. Additionally, watching the news emerged as a new factor post-test, with 1 respondent recognizing its importance. This suggests an increased awareness of the need to stay informed about current events as a means of being prepared for future uncertainties.

The post-test results reflect a nuanced understanding of what contributes to future confidence. There is a clear shift towards valuing practical skills, personal growth, and immediate support systems. While traditional education saw a decrease in importance, there was a notable rise in the value placed on green skills, personal development, and spiritual well-being. These insights suggest that respondents are adopting a more comprehensive approach to future confidence, balancing tangible skills with psychological and spiritual preparedness.

Table 13

Factors that will help the respondents to be confident about the future

FACTOR	PRE	POST
Environmental Actions		
Planting and caring for trees	2	1
Participate in social activities	8	4
Save water	4	4
Encourage and inform others	1	1
Protect the environment	10	10
Educational and Skills Development		
Education	22	7
Develop technological skills	0	1
Green skills	5	10
Personal Development		
Resilience	5	6
Self-confidence	4	7
Patience	1	4
Hard work and perseverance	3	4
Positivity	2	2
Decision-making and problem-solving skills	1	4
Confidence and overcoming shyness	1	2
Think about the future	1	2
Value mental health	1	1
Faith in God	0	7
Community Support		
Support from community	6	2
Support from friends and family	1	1
Positive role models	1	1
Follow elders	1	1
Motivation from parents	0	2
Preparedness		
Preparedness for calamities	7	8
Watch news	0	1

Environmentally Positive Actions

Respondents were also asked if they are currently taking any action for the environment. In the pre-test, 567 respondents answered affirmatively, while 152

responded negatively. In the post-test, 192 answered affirmatively, and 29 answered negatively. A follow-up question prompted respondents to list any environmental actions they were undertaking. These responses were then tabulated and cleaned to ensure only unique concepts from both lists were presented in a clear and organized manner.

Table 14

Environmentally positive actions the respondents do

ENVIRONMENTALLY POSITIVE ACTIONS	PRE-TEST	POST-TEST
Waste management	148	869
Planting trees	112	45
Calamity preparedness	51	13
Not burning garbage	33	12
Recycling	15	6
Conserving energy	8	16

Figure 10 shows that the most meaningful change was observed around waste management, with a major increase in focus post-intervention. This suggests that the educational program heightened awareness and action towards waste management. Calamity Preparedness, Not Burning Garbage, and Conserving Energy or Water, showed slight improvements, indicating some positive impact from the intervention; while Planting Trees, Farming, Clean-Up Drives, Information Campaigns, and Recycling, showed consistent but limited emphasis both before and after the intervention.

Figure 12

Environmentally positive actions the respondents do

Pre-test and post-test results of environmentally positive actions done by learners

The graph highlights the substantial impact of the HTH app on waste management, while other categories show marginal improvements or consistent focus. This indicates that the intervention successfully raised awareness and action in certain areas, particularly waste management, but further efforts may be needed to enhance focus on other environmental actions like tree planting, recycling, and clean-up drives.

What Young People Can Already Do

The survey asked the respondents to name some positive measures young people like themselves can already do to help the environment under different categories. Table 15 shows their answers.

Table 15

Top 8 responses of the participants across all areas

ENERGY CONSERVATION		FUEL CONSERVATION		GARDENING/COMPOSTING	
Turn off appliances when not in use	99	Use just enough fuel for cooking	29	Plant vegetables and fruits	78
Use solar energy	12	Use alternative fuels	18	Use biodegradable waste as fertilizer	12
Turn off lights when not needed	23	Plan meals to cook together	19	Use compost	8
Use electricity properly	14	Turn off the fire when not in use	5	Use recyclable containers for planting	8
Use LED lights	4	Use gas or LPG	6	Use fruit and vegetable peels as fertilizer	8
Reduce the use of appliances	6	Collect firewood	2	Use kitchen waste for compost	6
Use alternative items like fans	1	Use energy-efficient stoves	4	Bury organic waste in the ground	4
Use energy-efficient appliances	3	Use leftover firewood	3	Use leftover food as compost	4
TREE PLANTING		RECYCLING		WASTE REDUCTION	
Plant native trees to help the environment	15	Recycle materials to reduce waste	10	Avoid using plastic	8
Participate in tree planting activities	12	Create new items from recycled materials	8	Recycle materials	7
Plant trees in the backyard or farmland	10	Use recycled materials for home decor	7	Segregate waste and dispose properly	7
Plant fruit-bearing or non-fruit-bearing trees	8	Use plastic bottles for planting	7	Use eco bags for shopping	7
Planting helps prevent floods	8	Use old items for new purposes	5	Use reusable items	7
Tree planting for environmental benefits	6	Use craft skills to make decor from waste	5	Avoid single-use plastics	5
Plant trees to provide shade and fresh air	5	Separate waste for recycling	5	Reduce the use of plastic	5
Help with tree planting	5	Use waste to create planters	4	Reduce waste by buying only what is needed	5
ADVOCACY		COMMUTING		HEALTHY FOOD	
Educate about recycling	1	Walk to nearby places	8	Cook and eat vegetables	8
Support community cleaners	1	Walk to reduce pollution	8	Eat vegetables and fruits daily	7
Engage in waste reduction practices	1	Walk to save money	7	Eat healthy to maintain good health	7
Practice waste segregation at home	1	Use bike or scooter for transportation	5	Prepare nutritious meals	6
Recycle to reduce waste in landfills	1	Walk to avoid expenses	4	Include vegetables in meals	6
Use eco-friendly bags	1	Walk to reduce air pollution	4	Eat healthy to avoid illness	5
Avoid disposable plastic products	1	Walk as exercise	3	Avoid too much meat	4
Use compost to reduce waste	1	Walk to avoid using gas	3	Cooking for a healthy body	4

Many of their responses are common and reflect their domestic lives. The responses mirror a positive level of awareness and interest among students regarding environmental conservation and healthy living. Energy conservation, gardening, and waste reduction were top areas of focus, showing their commitment to small but impactful lifestyle changes.

However, there remains scope for improving habits around fuel conservation, waste management, and sustainable commuting. With continued education and advocacy, these young people can play a vital role in fostering a greener, healthier future.

The respondents provided responses across multiple categories, reflecting their awareness and engagement in environmentally friendly practices and healthy living habits.

Energy Conservation. The respondents highlighted the importance of turning off appliances when not in use, with the highest score of 22, showing a strong understanding of basic energy-saving habits. Other notable practices include using energy-efficient appliances (17) and using electricity properly (16), demonstrating a willingness to reduce energy consumption. Actions like reducing reliance on fans, heaters, or air conditioners were considered less frequent, with scores ranging from 5 to 8.

Fuel Conservation. Fuel-saving habits were also emphasized, with many respondents focusing on using just enough fuel for cooking (21) and planning meals

to cook together (13). The use of efficient fuels like biogas or LPG (10) and solar cookers (8) reflects an interest in sustainable fuel alternatives, though practices like using firewood selectively were less popular (4).

Gardening and Composting. The respondents showed strong enthusiasm for gardening and composting. Planting vegetables and fruits stood out with a high score of 28, indicating a popular and tangible environmental activity. Many of the respondents also recognized the benefits of using biodegradable waste as fertilizer (12) and composting (9). However, activities like using kitchen waste as compost and adopting vermicomposting received fewer mentions, with scores of 5 and 4, respectively.

Tree Planting. A sizable number of respondents expressed interest in tree planting to help the environment (22) and enhance local biodiversity (16). Planting trees for practical purposes, such as in school compounds or as windbreaks, also received moderate attention. However, fewer responses reflected awareness about the personal or economic benefits of tree planting, such as providing shade or creating future resources.

Recycling. In recycling, using old materials to reduce waste (12) emerged as the most widespread practice among the respondents, followed by recycling materials from nearby areas (8). While the respondents expressed interest in recycling paper and glass, less emphasis was placed on creative reuse like making new products from old materials (4).

Waste Reduction. Avoiding single-use plastics (10) and disposing of waste properly (9) were top concerns for the respondents in this category. This shows growing awareness about the environmental harm caused by improper waste management. However, avoiding disposable plastic items and minimizing non-biodegradable waste were less frequently mentioned, indicating a need for further education in these areas.

Advocacy. The respondents expressed interest in raising awareness about recycling (9) and engaging with teachers and peers to spread environmental consciousness (8). However, fewer responses reflected involvement in discussions at home or actively encouraging others to reduce waste.

Commuting. On commuting habits, the respondents mostly emphasized walking to nearby places (8) and using bicycles (6), highlighting eco-friendly transportation choices. However, practices like using public transport or carpooling received lower responses, showing room for improvement in promoting sustainable commuting.

Healthy Food and Living. In healthy living, the respondents prioritized drinking clean water (10) and eating vegetables and fruits daily (8), reflecting a focus on nutrition and well-being. Practices like avoiding junk food, washing food before eating, and cooking for a healthy body received moderate attention but need more encouragement to create lasting habits.

Post-Test Questions

Three additional questions were included in the post-test survey: 1) What are the first two important things you learned through HTH, 2) What are some other things you learned? and 3) If given the opportunity to change anything about how climate change was taught to you, what would it be?

Table 16 shows the top two things the respondents learned and their frequency, or how many of them gave the same responses.

Table 16
Top 2 things learned by the respondents

TOP 2 THINGS LEARNED

Green Skills	42
Sustainable Practices (e.g., recycling, waste segregation)	35
Environmental Protection	31
Preparedness for Natural Disasters	24
Green Jobs	15
Saving Resources (e.g., energy, water)	14
Job Application Skills (CV, cover letter)	7
Importance of Nature and Resources	6
Advocacy and Responsibility	5
Environmental Education and Community	4

Green Skills (42 mentions). This high frequency suggests a strong emphasis on developing skills that contribute to sustainable practices and environmental stewardship. It indicates that the respondents are gaining practical knowledge in areas like energy conservation, sustainable agriculture, and eco-friendly technologies.

Sustainable Practices (35 mentions). This includes activities such as recycling and waste segregation. The sizable number of mentions reflects the importance placed on teaching the respondents about reducing waste and managing resources efficiently, which are crucial for sustainable living.

Environmental Protection (31 mentions). This highlights a focus on measures and practices aimed at preserving natural habitats and biodiversity. It underscores the importance of instilling a sense of responsibility towards protecting the environment in the respondents.

Preparedness for Natural Disasters (24 mentions). This suggests that the program is also emphasizing the importance of being prepared for natural calamities. It includes training on disaster management and mitigation strategies, which are vital for resilience in the face of climate change.

Green Jobs (15 mentions). This indicates a growing awareness and interest in careers that contribute to environmental sustainability. It shows that the respondents are being educated on the various career opportunities available in the green economy.

Saving Resources (14 mentions). This includes strategies for conserving energy and water, which are essential for reducing the environmental footprint. It reflects an understanding of the importance of resource efficiency in everyday life.

Job Application Skills (7 mentions). The inclusion of skills related to applying for jobs, such as writing CVs and cover letters, suggests that the program also aims

to equip the respondents with the tools needed to secure employment in the green sector.

Importance of Nature and Resources (6 mentions). This shows an appreciation for the intrinsic value of nature and the need to protect natural resources. It highlights the educational efforts to foster a connection with and respect for the natural world.

Advocacy and Responsibility (5 mentions). This reflects the program's emphasis on encouraging the respondents to take active roles in advocating for environmental issues and taking responsibility for their actions.

Environmental Education and Community (4 mentions). This suggests that the program includes elements of environmental education and community engagement, promoting collective efforts towards sustainability.

The table indicates that the respondents have a good understanding of key concepts related to green skills and sustainability. It also shows that the program successfully imparts practical knowledge and skills that are essential for promoting environmental stewardship and resilience. The interest in green jobs, although not as high as other areas, still highlights a significant awareness among the respondents about the potential career paths in the green economy.

Table 17

Other things learned by the respondents.

LEARNED THINGS

Actions to take during a disaster	1	Making fertilizer from food waste	1
Appreciating natural resources and their proper use	1	Participating in projects and initiatives for nature	1
Awareness of Climate Change	1	Preparedness for Disasters	1
Being Active in Environmental Protection	2	Preparing a go-bag with necessary supplies for disasters	1
Being prepared for any disaster through proper preparation and knowledge	1	Preparing for Disasters	1
Being responsible in environmental protection	2	Preparing for Green Skills Lessons and Activities	1
Being responsible in waste segregation and proper disposal	2	Promoting responsible behavior in environmental care	1
Causes of climate change and steps to avoid it	1	Proper waste disposal	2
Characteristics and importance of green skills	1	Proper Waste Disposal and Recycling	2
Creating projects and initiatives for nature	1	Raising awareness about effective ways to prevent environmental damage	1
Different green jobs and activities to reduce greenhouse gases	1	Raising awareness on the importance of nature protection	1
Green jobs and their contributions to the environment	1	Saving electricity, walking, and using public transport	1
Green Skills	2	Sharing knowledge about environmental care	1
How to stay safe during any disaster	1	Sharing knowledge and skills on green skills with others	1
Importance of being aware of climate change and ways to reduce it	1	Steps to take before, during, and after a disaster	1
Importance of green jobs in environmental protection and human safety	1	Teaching Green Skills to Others	1
Knowledge of Climate Change and How to Avoid It	1	Training and acquiring green skills for various jobs	1
Knowledge of Green Skills and Green Jobs	1	Tree planting and growing other plants to help the environment	1
Learning the importance of green skills and their impact on daily life	1	Types of jobs that help the environment	1
Learning ways to protect nature	1	Understanding Green Jobs and Green Skills	1
Advocacy and Responsibility	5		
Environmental Education and Community	4		

Green Jobs

The survey responses indicate that while the respondents have a general understanding of green jobs and show interest in pursuing them, there are substantial barriers that need to be addressed.

Table 18

Examples of green jobs, and what prevents people from finding a green job

Examples of Green Jobs	Green Jobs of Interest	Reasons Preventing or Hindering from Getting a Green Job
Agriculturalist	Agriculturist	Lack of knowledge
Environmentalist	Tree Planting	No knowledge
Recycling	Planting	Laziness
Environmental Advocate	Recycling	Salary
Renewable Energy	Agricultural	Lack of confidence
Renewable Energy Technician	Environmental Technician	Trash
Street Sweeper	Farming	Lack of knowledge and government support
Lawyer	Forestry	Climate change
Green Construction	Government Employee	Financial
Marine Biologist	Manufacturing	Green job knowledge (not aware or unsure)
Solar Panel Technician	Mechanic	Lack of knowledge and skills
Teacher	Nurse	Lack of organization
Tree Planting	Organic Farmer	Lack of specialized training
Waste Management Specialist	Composting	Lack of funds
Environmental Consultant	Planting Plants	Low salary
Food Technologist	Social Worker	No support from organizations
Mechanic	Street Cleaners	Busy or no time for green skills
Nurse	Street Sweeper	Confidence
Ecologist	Sustainability Consultant	Deforestation
Environmental Engineer	TUPAD	Di maayos na pagtatapon ng basura
Farmer	Agricultural Specialist	Experience
Gardening/Plant Tito	Climate Change	Gadget

Survey responses provide insight into their understanding and interest in green jobs, as well as the challenges they face in pursuing such careers. These

include improving awareness and education about green jobs, providing better organizational and governmental support, and addressing financial and training needs. Addressing these challenges will be crucial in fostering a new generation of professionals committed to sustainability and environmental stewardship.

Knowledge and Examples of Green Jobs. The respondents demonstrated a varied understanding of green jobs. Some of the jobs they identified included: Agriculturist (3 mentions), Environmentalist, Environmental, Advocate, and Environmental Consultant (collectively 3 mentions); jobs related to renewable energy, such as Renewable Energy Technician and Solar Panel Technician (2 mentions); waste management roles like Recycling and Waste Management Specialist (2 mentions); traditional environmental roles like Marine Biologist, Environmental Engineer, and Environmental Consultant (3 mentions); practical green jobs such as Street Sweeper and Green Construction (2 mentions); less traditional roles identified as green jobs included Lawyer, Teacher, Mechanic, and Nurse (4 mentions).

These responses show that the respondents recognize both conventional environmental careers and other roles that can contribute to sustainability efforts.

Interest in Green Jobs. When asked which green jobs they are most interested in, the respondents highlighted several roles: Agriculturist and Tree Planters were the most frequently mentioned, with each receiving 3 mentions; other roles that sparked interest included painting, recycling, environmental technician, and organic farmer (each receiving 1-2 mentions).

Some of the respondents expressed interest in specialized fields such as Environmental Technician, Climate Change Specialist, and Sustainability Consultant (3 mentions).

Challenges in Pursuing Green Jobs. Under this category, the respondents identified several barriers that prevent or hinder them from pursuing green jobs:

The most common barrier was a lack of knowledge, cited by 11 respondents. Laziness and salary concerns were also significant hurdles, each mentioned by 5 respondents. Other obstacles included a lack of confidence, inadequate organizational support, financial constraints, and insufficient specialized training (each mentioned by 2-4 respondents). Additional reasons included lack of government support, trash management issues, and a general lack of awareness about green jobs.

Conclusion

The intervention program conducted by Plan International Pilipinas, utilizing the *Hope Town Hero* app, has proven to be an effective method for enhancing climate change knowledge among students from Samar, Occidental Mindoro, and Maguindanao. The program included a diverse group of participants: 164 males (22.81%), 445 females (61.89%), 6 non-binary (0.83%), and 7 participants who preferred not to say (0.97%) during the pre-test phase. Post-test demographics showed engagement from 69 males (31.51%), 148 females (67.58%), 1 non-binary, and 1 participant who preferred not to say.

The program's two-phase approach, starting with a pre-test to establish baseline knowledge and concluding with a post-test after using the app, demonstrated significant improvements in both male and female participants' understanding and interest in climate change. For male participants, the average pre-test score of 0.95 rose to 3.59 in the post-test. Similarly, female participants saw their average scores increase from 0.78 to 3.47.

This substantial growth in scores highlights the app's effectiveness in not only elevating knowledge levels but also engaging students more deeply with the subject matter. The demographic distribution underscores the broad reach and inclusivity of the program, addressing diverse groups within the student population.

This outcome suggests that digital tools and interactive learning methods can play a crucial role in environmental education, making complex topics more accessible and engaging for young learners. Consequently, integrating such innovative approaches into educational programs can significantly contribute to fostering a more informed and proactive generation in the fight against climate change. The success of this program underscores the potential for similar initiatives to be implemented on a broader scale, ultimately aiding in the global effort to mitigate climate change through education and awareness.

Recommendations

The survey asked the respondents what they might suggest improving further the *Hope Town Hero* app. These are 1) Using contemporary characters, 2)

Ensuring that learning is not interrupted by making sure the game does not lag between characters, 3) Allow sharing of information so users can improve their social skills, 4) Availability of a demonstration how to use the app, 5) Interaction with experts, 6) Personalized learning and progress tracking, 7) Make it more interactive so it is less boring, 8) Make an actual application of green skills a part of the game, 9) Video presentations, 10) Interactive tools to make the app more engaging, 11) Questions should not be repetitive, and 12) The user interface.

These suggestions already encapsulate what users look for in gamified learning. Gabriela Kiryakoval, et. al., in “Gamification of education,” emphasizes that today's learners are citizens of the digital world. Growing up in a world that is becoming increasingly digital, they have somehow developed more sophisticated learning styles than their predecessors.²³ Educators today must face the challenge of adapting their teaching techniques to the learning styles of their students. Gamification is one of the styles they can employ to make the teaching-learning process more fun and interesting.

The necessity to make use of this strategy stems from what educators have always known: Motivation is the first step to comprehension. It is what fuels learning.²⁴ Therefore, one can say, motivation is to a student as gasoline is to a car. And because children learn through play, games are an effective motivation for them. Hence, gamification as a fusion of play and learning can be an effective tool in

²³ "(PDF) GAMIFICATION ELEMENTS AND THEIR IMPACTS ON TEACHING AND LEARNING" 01 Dec. 2018, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339236007_GAMIFICATION_ELEMENTS_AND_THEIR_IMPACTS_ON_TEACHING_AND_LEARNING_-_A_REVIEW.

²⁴ "Types of Motivation in Education | Intrinsic & Extrinsic Effects." 17 Nov. 2021, <https://www.highspeedtraining.co.uk/hub/motivation-in-education/>.

the hand of a teacher not only to motivate but to continue to engage their students throughout the class period.

Kiryakoal discusses what makes a play. 1) Everyone is a participant, 2) There are clear objectives, 3) It has a point system, and points are accumulated based on accomplished tasks, 4) It has levels based on the points garnered, 5) At some point, players are rewarded based on achievements, and 6) Depending on merits or demerits, a player moves conversely, demerits, they move up and down ranks.

Another key element of play is simulation where a player becomes a character in the game in an environment that semblances real life. The gameplay environment is designed to engage the total person and aims primarily to make playtime as entertaining as possible.

When used in education, the entertainment part becomes a bridge between teacher and student to transmit knowledge from one end to another.

This is the principle behind edutainment, a word coined by B.F. Skinner in application of his theory, which supports the belief that a person's eagerness to learn is motivated by reward and punishment.²⁵ Edutainment is a predecessor of gamification, which has now become a by-word in academic circles in consideration of the needs of 21st-century learners. Since children and youth today are digital natives, gamification appeals to them.

²⁵ "B.F. Skinner: Operant Conditioning and Behaviourism Theories." 27 Aug. 2024, <https://www.earlyyears.tv/b-f-skinner-operant-conditioning-and-behaviourism-theories/>.

Based on the above, the following recommendations are given as a guide in the design and development of the *Hope Town Hero* app. As an educational app to teach climate change, HTH's curriculum should be interdisciplinary.

Revisit and Redesign the Curriculum

As an educational app, HTH should be guided by a curriculum. Plan International Pilipinas already has an existing curriculum for climate education, and it is recommended that HTH be in sync with it. However, the said curriculum lacks objectives and measures that correspond to HTH, or vice versa. If this app were to be the mainstay of Plan International as its noble gift to humanity, it should be developed alongside Plan International's curriculum.

K-12 Curriculum Mapping

In addition, if it were to be used in the Philippines for Filipino children, knowing that the success DepEd has a big role in educating young Filipinos on the environment and climate change, HTH's curriculum should be in line with DepEd's K-12 and MATATAG agenda, so that any teacher in a public school would know where and where to use HTH or Plan International's curriculum should they decide on integrating the same in their subjects. DepEd already has an existing curriculum for climate, and HTH can be an excellent supplement to reinforce teachings on the environment.

App Rewards for Graded Points. The app can be designed in such a way that a user, after reaching a certain level in the app, can show an online badge to their teacher and earn points to be added to their grade. The app can also be used as a

performance task and should have a feature by which a user is told to plant a tree or collect biodegradables for compost, take a selfie, and post the picture on their school's Facebook page, Twitter, Instagram, or any available social media.

Spiral Progression. Spiral progression is a strategy in curriculum development on which the design of DepEd's K-12 curriculum is based. In this setup, a teacher begins with basic concepts at the initial stage of the teaching-learning process. Over time, teachers and students spiral up and learn more complex concepts. This is done gradually and hinges on achieving some level of mastery.

To fully incorporate the principles of gamification in the HTH app, it should have, if it does not yet have, levels of difficulty in line with the spiral progression design of K-12. It is personalized in the sense that a user registers their name and date of birth and, depending on their age and grade level, starts at a certain stage in the game.

Interdisciplinary Gamifying Experience. One of the aspirations of environmental advocates is for climate change education to be treated as a body of knowledge in itself, which means that it should be taught as a subject in the national curriculum so that more focus is given to the development of the knowledge, behavior, and skills of learners in so far as the environment is concerned. There is still a long road to travel for this, but DepEd has been mandated by law to require teachers to integrate climate change in their lessons.

For HTH to be relevant in the wide spectrum of the K-12 curriculum, its curriculum must include competencies and skills from other subjects, such as

general science, biology, mathematics, history, geography, and economics, among many others.

In addition, an app that gamifies climate change education should have formative and summative tests, which can be considered a part of mid-term or periodical exams.

Teachers Can Also Play. The gap in climate change education can be bridged when climate change education is already given special attention with a serious intent to make our children lovers of nature and protectors of the environment and when teachers, who are the implementers of this curriculum, are already armed with enough knowledge and are already passionate about the health of the planet to persuasively deliver lessons on the eventual degradation of world's habitats due to climate change and global warming.

HTH can be an instrument to help achieve this. A gamifying app can be appealing even to them when it is packed with information that they can use to arouse their learners' interest. Therefore, HTH should have various game tracks, and one of these should be for educators who want to learn new things while playing a game.

For added fun, teachers can take an online exam, which can be a feature of the app, and when successful can be issued a certificate by Plan International, which DepEd can by allocating certain continuing education units for it.

This way, DepEd and Plan International Pilipinas can be partners for the environment and be called hope town heroes.

Focus on the Objectives. Table 2 is a simple representation of how HTH can effectively help in the development of the total child. Any teacher is familiar with the three areas of development which target the mind, heart, and will of an individual. Every lesson plan should take into consideration these three areas. Thus, they should always include three objectives, namely, cognitive (mind), affective (heart), psychosocial (will).

The first appeals to knowledge (what the child must know); the second, to emotions (what does a child should feel); and action (what a child should do in response). HTH game levels should be modularized and observe how DepEd curriculum move gradually and spirally progress, which means that everything that a child should encounter in that stage or level must contribute toward the achievement of these objectives, which are measured through how they perform , and experience, will they be able to comprehend or perform the task to be required), relevant (Does the learner need this knowledge and competence in this day and age, or in his daily life), and time bound (How long can this module be reasonably accomplished).

A successful implementation of a curriculum depends on a strategic delivery of lessons prescribed in that curriculum. As an app that gamifies learning on climate change, HTH should incorporate in its lessons (modular game levels) the key elements of gamification.

Each module should have the following characteristics in relation to the cognitive, affective, and psychosocial development of HTH's user.

As a tool that is both educational and developmental, the app's design should prioritize the holistic development of individuals by addressing the cognitive, affective, and psychosocial domains.

Cognitive Development. By engaging with HTH at various stages, learners will acquire age-appropriate knowledge and skills while developing critical thinking abilities, demonstrated through the analysis and interpretation of data presented in the app. Given the technical nature of climate change, this 21st-century skill is essential for effective problem-solving. To foster and challenge these skills, HTH should incorporate gamified activities strategically throughout its content.

Furthermore, a gamified educational app on climate change is inherently interdisciplinary. HTH can deliver relevant knowledge across subjects such as science, geography, history, current events, and more. It can immerse users in gamified scenarios where they apply this knowledge—such as understanding and interpreting data or solving real-world problems—enhancing both learning and engagement.

Affective Development. As learners acquire new knowledge through HTH at various stages, they will develop a heightened awareness of the environment.

This affective development is reflected in their ability to internalize the importance of caring for the Earth, showing empathy for vulnerable communities and concern for future generations.

Psychosocial Development. By engaging with HTH at various stages, learners will acquire age-appropriate knowledge and skills that empower them to connect with peers and actively engage their communities on environmental issues.

The app's name, *Hope Town Hero*, reflects its objective to cultivate leadership among the youth. To achieve this, the app should be designed to facilitate collaboration, enabling users to connect through the platform itself, social media, or in-person interactions. This will allow them to work together on solutions to problems presented within the app. Through these collaborative efforts, learners will develop and demonstrate resilience and adaptability as they work with limited resources to devise practical solutions, exhibiting a sense of responsibility and community engagement.

Table 19 summarizes the above objectives in all development areas. These suggested skills and competencies may be used as a guide in the development of the app should it incorporate gamifying elements, such as levels of difficulty, leaderboard, and rewards and punishment.

Table 19Sample skills / competencies that may be developed in a user of *Hope Town Hero*

Area	Skills	Competencies
Cognitive	Understanding climate change	Grasping the basics of climate change, its causes, and effects. Recognizing the importance of reducing carbon footprints.
	Critical thinking and problem solving	Analyzing environmental issues and their potential solutions. Developing strategies for sustainable living and resource management.
	Knowledge of Renewable Energy	Learning about various sources of renewable energy and their benefits. Understanding how renewable energy can replace fossil fuels.
	Recycling and Waste Management	Identifying recyclable materials and understanding the recycling process. Learning how to manage waste effectively to reduce environmental impact.
	Water Conservation Techniques	Learning practical ways to reduce water usage at home and in the community.
Affective	Environmental Stewardship	Developing a sense of responsibility towards protecting the environment. Cultivating a passion for nature and wildlife conservation.
	Empathy and Compassion	Understanding the impact of climate change on different communities and species. Developing empathy for those affected by environmental degradation.
	Commitment to Sustainable Practices	Fostering a personal commitment to adopt and promote sustainable practices. Building a lifestyle that prioritizes environmental health.
Psycho-social	Collaboration and Teamwork	Working effectively with others to achieve common environmental goals. Participating in community projects and initiatives for environmental protection.
	Advocacy and Leadership	Developing skills to advocate for environmental policies and practices. Leading initiatives and campaigns to raise awareness about climate change.
	Community Engagement	Engaging with local communities to promote sustainable practices. Organizing and participating in community events focused on environmental issues.
	Communication Skills	Effectively communicating the importance of climate action to peers and adults. Using various platforms to spread awareness and educate others about climate change.

Repetitive Learning Feature. *Repetitio est mater studiorum* is a long-held principle in education which translates, Repetition is the mother of learning. The spiral progression design of the K-12 curriculum hinges on the proper administration of the BCM and requires a level of mastery before a learner can advance to the next level. To ensure a level of mastery is reached, repetitive learning thus plays a crucial role.

As it allows a student to be exposed or tasked to do the same thing repeatedly (the standard being 8-10 times), the required knowledge or expected competence can be committed to the mind for good.²⁶ HTH should have this feature, allowing multiple recitals of a concept or performance of a task on to mastery.

Along this path is the goal to form good habits among HTH users. The app's leaderboard should have a system by which it can track how many times a certain action, such as throwing trash properly, is done by a user. If a user has done something 16 times or more, they will be awarded a good habit badge.

Allows Multiple Paths. The survey conducted by Plan International shows that there is a significant difference between a male's and female's knowledge and perception of climate change. A person's gender or sexuality, which may dictate their role in society, can influence their attitude toward the environment and their estimation of their vulnerability under the threats of climate change and global warming. It is recommended that the gamifying app consider a different approach

²⁶ "Repetition is the First Principle of All Learning - ResearchGate." 17 Aug. 2001, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228318502_Repetition_is_the_First_Principle_of_All_Learning.

for each gender. But the HTH development team should be careful not to put in a box the personhood of an individual by stereotyping gender identity.

Addressing the Gap Between Genders. This feature can be helpful in addressing the gap between male and female. The survey shows that in most areas male respondents are on the lead. Even after HTH intervention, while their scores significantly improved, they are still behind compared with the male group. An educational app like HTH should consider that between sexes or across sexual orientations, preferences, or gender identities, differences in knowledge, behavior, and skills are to be expected. Teachers managing a heterogenous class should be sensitive to these differences that could influence learning style and comprehension. This is particularly important for such an app as HTH. The elderly, women, and children are considered most vulnerable to calamities and natural disasters.

It is women who are often left at home. In a typical Filipino household, women are the caregivers of the family. They look after not only their children but even their parents if they are still alive. During calamities, it is these women who are first in the frontline to protect their loved ones.

An educational app on climate change must specially target women. They should know what it is and what kind of dangers it brings to their community. To be empowered by education and be given a voice and stage, women can be medics or nurses, even cooks, or teachers of children who have also been displaced. An app that allows multiple paths for more flexibility and to give various situations other

users can relate to, makes itself accessible to the vulnerable, and a tool for their empowerment.

Hope Town Hero Image

The following design standards are mere recommendations, or a gentle reminder, notwithstanding the fact that Plan International is a worldwide organization and, most probably, it already has a set of rules to maintain its own standards. However, an app needs to appeal to the status, which dictates the preference or taste of its intended users. In marketing, the first impression is important.

A 21st-century child has access to a mobile phone and their choices of apps are limitless. A person who browses an online app store may, as a force of habit, may click on an app, familiar or unfamiliar to him, because something has caught their attention or appealed to their tastes. All it takes is a second or a fraction of it to make that decision.

An app's first touch with its intended users is what the eyes can first see and what the ears can hear, as these precede actual app experience.

Marketing Collaterals

Recommendations in this area are limited to only six things. It is, however, recommended that a marketing plan be drawn up prior to launching HTH.

Logo. The app logo should be designed to appeal to children and young people, especially because, although they do not yet know the industrial standard for logo design, they have already probably seen hundreds of thousands of logos and

exposure to them molded their taste. As a marketing strategy, Plan International can perhaps conduct a nationwide logo making contest.

Color Scheme. The color scheme may or may not be consistent with the official color scheme of the organization. This is a management decision, but it should be bright colors that appeal to children and young people and represent the environment.

Font Types. HTH is an educational app, and so font style should look scholastic, but not too formal. Also, the app is to be used by children who are being taught at school the proper way of writing. It is recommended that HTH follows these standards to be consistent with what the children are learning at school. For users in the primary, there must be only a few words and not more than two lines.

Notification Sounds and Background Music. Successful online games and apps not only have tasteful logos, appealing color schemes, and font types; they also have distinct sounds and background music. These should also be considered in HTH's design.

A Note on Adultification

Hope Town Hero's themes and visuals should be consistent with its image and should be representative of its name and mission. Aesthetics should be child friendly, however, the HTH development team should take into consideration the phenomenon called "precocious maturity" or "adultification." This means that some children are taking on adult responsibilities and display adult behaviors.

Caused by social pressures, economic factors, poor parenting, or exposure to adult contents, this phenomenon is also called “early maturation.” Children who experience this shun childhood, such that they no longer want to be seen playing with toys or wearing apparel for children.

A theme song will help promotion and retention. A good theme song, such as Superbook’s can be sung or hummed over and over, and it can help bring the message to people.

HTH’s theme and visuals should, therefore, not be too childish but still appealing and reflective of children’s and young people’s energy and zest for life.

Core Features and Game Structure

To design an engaging environmental education app for children that teaches climate change using gamification elements, it is essential to blend fun, interactivity, and learning.

Interactive Storytelling. HTH should be designed as a heroic adventure to save the planet and its inhabitants. As a *Hope Town Hero*, the player is the main character in that adventure and his task is to salvage Earth from further decline by solving environmental challenges.

Every adventure has a hero and a villain, and then it develops as follows:

Pre-Adventure. Upon registration, a user indicates name, date of birth, gender, and location. This will logarithmically prompt the system to load modules that are appropriate for their gender and grade level. Users get to choose an avatar (but the app should have more personalization features). UI can be localized

depending on where the user is located. Local environmental issues should therefore be used so that the player can relate to the story and be made aware of the condition of their locality.

The Setting. The setting of the story is Hope Town, but this can be localized to the user's vernacular, Tagalized, Cebuanized, or whatever.

The Hero and the Villain. This researcher believes that the premise of the app's name is that every one of us can be our planet's hero. The author imagines the story to begin like this: "... And so, while our hero enjoys a walk in Hope Town Plaza, a mysterious dark cloud appears suddenly in the sky. As its shadow covers the entire town center, a horrendous, choking smell seems to ooze out of it and flows down surreally like murky water from a polluted river.

That dark cloud is in fact a transporter. Composed primarily of CO₂, N₂O, and CH₄, it is one of a kind, and the only one which bears the brand and banner of Mutatio Climatis, the global headquarters of the evil Globus Flamma or Global Fire. He leads a horde of pollutants called Worldthreaters whose mission is to bring about climate change with the goal of raising the planet's global temperature to 2 degrees Celsius which means death to millions of Earth's inhabitants.

Our hero runs for safety, but he hears a mysterious voice, which tells him, "Why are you afraid? You are my child; you have my power, and you must fight!" As the voice fades away into the horizon, the ordinary boy suddenly feels strong. <Theme song plays, and magic happens. VFX.> He does not fight alone. Why should

he? Mother Earth has already called to his aid a cohort of fighters called The Advocates...”

Gamification Elements. Game dynamics should incorporate the elements of gamification, and there must be a balance between fun and learning. Discussed in this paper’s Review of Related Literature are the goals and pitfalls of gamification, and how they can be avoided. One of them is to be defocused from the goal of education to bring about positive change in the behavior and conduct of an individual. The game dynamics for HTH must adapt to the following game elements.

The Goal. The goal of the game is for the hero (the user) to save the planet and its inhabitants from Globus Flamma and his horde of pollutants called EarthThreaters.

Characters. The main character is helped by the Advocates, a group of Earth lovers who possess superpowers to counter the pollution Globus wants to spread all over the world so the Earth’s surface temperature may increase to 2 degrees, thereby, death-sentencing many of its inhabitants.

The Mission. Hope town heroes, as they are called, must do everything in their power to prevent this from happening.

Excitement Booster. All throughout the game, an animated thermometer will report and show emotions of happiness, excitement, fear, and many others as it reports every now and then the temperature of the plant. The game is over when it reaches 2 degrees.

Current Events. Today's real life hope town heroes in the person of the late Miss Gina Lopez and Barbados' Prime Minister Mia Motley, and the like will make an appearance to advise, comfort, or encourage Earth's defenders.

Rewards and Punishment. They will be rewarded based on their actions, which can be counted as points. For instance, if they plant a tree, or convince a community to do coastal clean-up, temperatures will drop. Otherwise, it will progress to 2 degrees. For added fun, rewards and badges will be given and the player is given a title and corresponding power progressively.

Leaderboard. Rewards and awards can be displayed in the UI for motivation and friendly competition.

Levels of Difficulty. Each level focuses on a specific topic, such as energy conversion, waste reduction, tree planting, and others). To move to the level, players solve a puzzle, answer a question, or perform a task.

Learning Methods and Activities. Name-a-Tree contests, Clean-a-River relay, Garbage Bin Hop, or Read-Me-A-Chart are some of HTH's employed teaching methods. In addition to riddle-solving games, quizzes, or Create and Habituate tasks that challenge the player to create a healthy habit for either aquatic, forest, or even backyard insects and reptiles. This will evaluate their knowledge of what kind of environment these creatures need to survive.

Real-Life Application. The app gives instructions to the user, such as, to turn off unused electric fans, light, and others.

Teachers and Parents Dashboard. Child's tasks done offline will be reported to a teacher or parent who records them on their dashboard.

Social Engagement. With parental guidance, such activities will be allowed and will also accumulate points for the user, such as joining a clean-up drive, or a tree planting event.

Advocacy Linkages. One important topic that must be included in the app is advocacies. The app can have a database of advocacies, and one competency that it should aim to develop among users is finding which organization to tap to solve a specific problem. This will emphasize the universality Climate change issues and that the war against the same is not supposed to be fought by just one person or one group, but everybody's contribution should be tapped or welcomed.

This HTH feature will emphasize the need for collaboration, and will develop leadership skills by means of coordinating among different NGOs and assigning them specific tasks to do.

For example, the user is prompted with the following:

“Emergency! The residents of Hope Town are getting sick for reasons still unknown. The following symptoms are observed: Vomiting and Diarrhea, leading to dehydration and shock. Your task is to find out the cause of the problem and present solutions to it.”

The user will then be presented with a table of steps that should be done. He will arrange these steps in proper order.

Once the problem has been identified, they will be asked to come up with short-term and long-term solutions. In this regard, they will be presented with a list of NGOs they can contact and assign to each solution given.

Points will be accumulated based on how accurately these are done.

For learners in the higher grade, after successfully completing this module, they can be asked to identify environmental problems in their community and determine which advocacy group they can contact to help solve the problem.

Periodic Evaluation

A special body within the organization should be formed to conduct a continuous evaluation of HTH. The following is a table of KPIs that are recommended for the evaluation of the app. These are based on Palombi's and Theodotou's suggestions.

Table 20
Recommended KPI for HTH

KPIs	Description
Daily Active Users (DAU) and Monthly Active Users (MAU)	The organization should keep track of the number of users who download and use the app daily and monthly.
Session length and frequency	The average number of times the app is used and for how long.
Retention	The number of users who continue to use the app, and for how long.
Learning objectives are met	Give summative and formative tests in an entertaining fashion to measure learning and mastery.
Peer teaching	The best measure of learning is when a learner can share with others what they have learned.
Environmental impact	Measure the collective environmental impact (e.g., carbon emissions saved, amount of CO2 offset).
Sustainability (longitudinal consideration)	Observe each learner for how long they will practice what they have learned.

Growth metrics	Based on demographics, track down how many have downloaded the app, their location, gender, age, ethnicity, and many others, compared with those who had abandoned it after some time.
App performance	Track the number of times the app experienced a downtime or crashed.

A big area of consideration in their evaluation is curriculum review. Should PIP decide on collaborating with DepEd, it should be up to date with changes in their curriculum. Participating schools can also provide HTH with data from students on student performance and HTH, the continuing development of which being data-driven and curriculum-based.

The surveys proved that the HTH app helped to improve the knowledge of the respondents on Climate change. Effectively, it also demonstrated more concern for the environment by an increase of their interest in key areas and eagerness to perform certain tasks to help the environment.

The HTH app can be an effective tool in raising the awareness of children and youth on climate change, and this researcher believes that the best way to maximize its impact is through partnership with DepEd to incorporate HTH in their curriculum. As discussed in the recommendations, HTH can also be used to encourage people to know more about Climate change and teach about it more passionately.